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DID INDO-EUROPEAN LANGUAGES STEM FROM A TRANS-EURASIAN ORIGINAL LANGUAGE? AN INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This interdisciplinary study allowed me to establish, on the basis of linguistic, genetic, archaeological, historical and religious data, that linguistic concordances between Gaulish and Slavic were linked with Neolithic migrations from North-Western India and Pakistan to Iran, Mesopotamia, Anatolia, the Caucasus, the North of the Black Sea, Danubic and Balkan Europe, Gaul and Iberia, where Neolithic farmers contributed to the formation of the megalithic civilisation which developed in Gaul from 5.000 BC and brought an archaic language stemming from a Trans-Eurasian original language. This explains the linguistic concordances I established between Gaulish and Dravidian languages - 250 common words from the 500 words I studied (and 160 with Burushaski), as well as with Altaic, Uralic, Kartvelian, Anatolian and Middle-Eastern languages. This also explains similarities I have found in the organisation of the Society and religion, which lead certain researchers to suggest, on the basis of the spread of the very ancient haplogroup H2 P-96 from India to Western Europe, that first Europeans and proto-Dravidians had a very ancient common origin, as the macrohaplogroup F and the haplogroup H could appear in India.

Cette étude interdisciplinaire m'a permis de démontrer, sur la base de données linguistiques, génétiques, archéologiques, historiques et religieuses, que les correspondances linguistiques entre le gaulois et le slave étaient liées à des migrations Néolithiques d'Inde et du Pakistan du Nord-Ouest vers l'Iran, la Mésopotamie, l'Anatolie, le Caucase, le Nord de la Mer Noire, l'Europe danubienne et balkanique, la Gaule et l'Ibérie, où les agriculteurs néolithiques ont contribué à former la civilisation mégalithique qui s'est développée en Gaule à partir de -5.000 et apporté une langue archaïque issue d'une langue originelle trans-eurasienne. Cela explique les correspondances linguistiques que j'ai établies entre le gaulois et les langues dravidiennes - 250 mots communs sur les 500 mots étudiés (et 160 avec le bourouchaski), ainsi qu'avec les langues altaïques, ouraliennes, karvéliennes, anatoliennes et moyen-orientales. Cela explique aussi les similitudes constatées dans l'organisation de la société et la religion, qui amènent certains chercheurs à suggérer, sur la base de la diffusion du très ancien haplogroupe H2 P-96 de l'Inde à l'Europe de l'Ouest, que les premiers Européens et les proto-Dravidiens avaient une origine commune très ancienne, le macrohaplogroupe F et l'haplogroupe H ayant pu apparaître en Inde.

KEYWORDS: PIE reconstruction, trans-Eurasian language, historical linguistics, ancient history, ancient archaeology, aDNA research, ancient migrations, ancient religions

1. INTRODUCTION

Gaulish was an ancient Celtic language that was spoken in parts of Continental Europe before and during the period of the Roman Empire. (Eska 2008; Watkins 1999, p. 6; McCone 1996). The Slavic languages, also known as the Slavonic languages, are Indo-European languages spoken primarily by the Slavic peoples or their descendants. The current geographical distribution of natively spoken Slavic languages includes the Balkans, Central and Eastern Europe, and all the way from Western Siberia to the Russian Far East. (Lockwood 1972; Novotna, Blažek 2007; Schenker 2002). Starting from a linguistic study about linguistic concordances between Gaulish and Slavic languages (Orr 1992), I discovered that the etymology of Gaulish and Slavic words isn't exclusively Indo-European and also shows concordances with Dravidian, Altaic, Uralic, Kartvelian, Anatolian and Middle-Eastern languages, as well as with Burushaski, an archaic language which raised numerous controversies between researchers about his supposed Indo-European or Dene-Caucasian origin. This led me to investigate further ancient migrations with an interdisciplinary approach combining genetic, archaeological, historical and religious data in order to find a common denominator between all these languages, which would be from my point of view an archaic Trans-Eurasian language, which split later into these language families and originated from Central Asia.

There are two main theories for the peopling of Europe and the formation of Indo-European languages. Gimbutas' (1997) conventional Theory of Kurgans, summarized below, also advocated by the geneticist Bernard Sécher in his blogs referenced in fine, places the original homeland of Indo-European languages in the Pontic steppes around 6.000 BC. Renfrew's (1987) alternative theory links the formation of Indo-European languages to the migration of agriculture from Anatolia to Europe 8.000 to 9.500 years ago. This theory seems to me more suitable to explain the formation of archaic Balkan languages, and more globally of archaic European languages as Gaulish, given their links with Dravidian and Caucasian languages.

The present paper is a critical overview of the origin of the Indo-European languages through an interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approach.

1.1 *The theory of Kurgans*

According to the Theory of Kurgans, one half of present-day Europeans stem from the Yamna steppe riders who, coming from the Caucasus and Iran, and perhaps even from the mountains of Altay, Pamir and Hindu-Kush, settled down in the steppes of Southern

Russia and Ukraine in contact with proto-Slavic sedentary populations, as these of the Cucuteni-Tripolje culture (which could be from my viewpoint of Dravidian origin, as the cultures of Vinča, Butmir and Visoko). The Yamna culture is genetically linked up to 75% with corded ware and battle axe cultures, which expanded from Russia to Baltic countries, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Germany and Gaul. These cultures would be at the origin of Indo-European languages and Slavic, Germanic and Celtic peoples, explaining similarities between Gaulish, Slavic and Indo-European languages.

According to this theory, the Indo-Europeanisation followed the progress of the culture of Kurgans, which came in the Russo-Ukrainian steppe from central Siberia in 5.000 BC. The first wave of migration, around 4.400/4.200 BC, created the Anatolian group. The second, around 3.400/3.200 BC, created the Phrygians, Germans, Balto-Slavs, Illyrians and Celts. The third, around 3.000/2.800 BC, created the Daco-Thracians, Greeks, Armenians and Indo-Iranians. The Germans, Balts, Slavs, Celts, Italics, Illyrians and Phrygians all come from the Kurgan culture by the culture of corded ware, and the Indo-Iranians are connected by the culture of Andronovo. Let's have a closer look to the second wave, which took place around 3400/3200 BC at the end of Kurgan III and migrated in all directions from the "kurganised" territories of the North West of the Black Sea, where was formed the culture of Usatovo, fusion of Kurgan and Cucuteni cultures. This second wave collided to the South with the culture of Cernavoda I, which representatives had to retreat to the South to settle in Macedonia, Bulgaria and down to Western Anatolia, noticeably in Troy. The cultures of Cucuteni-Tripolye, Vinča, Butmir and Petresti, in the Balkans, were dismantled. A new cultural entity developed in the Balkano-Danubic region by the fusion of the cultures of Cernavoda I and "Ancient Europe". It was named Cernavoda III in Romania, Boleraz in Slovakia and Baden in Austria. Creating a vast "Balkano-Danubic" cultural complex, it extended its influence to all the Danube basin from Romania and Bulgaria to Yugoslavia, Hungary, Czechoslovakia, Austria and Southern and Central Germany to the Lake of Constance and Nordlingen Ries, where it gave birth to the ceramics of Furchenstich and the culture of Rössen III. In the middle of the IVth millennium, the "kurganisation" of the upper basin of the Danube created the cultures of Mondsee, Altheim and Pfyn. The Kurgan funeral rituals imposed themselves in the region of the Elbe and the Saale and in Bohemia. The Kurgan culture expanded in the Northern plain, provoking the mutation of the Bell Beaker culture in globular amphora culture, and then corded ware culture. In the

last quarter of the IVth millennium, the cultural map of Europe was totally renewed. The Celtic civilisation was born from the cultures of Urnfields, Hallstatt and La Tène, stemming from the cultures of Unetice and Vučedol, which were born from the culture of Baden, stemming from a “kurganisation” of local cultures of “Ancient Europe” (Gimbutas, 1997). This theory at-tests of ancient contacts between Celts and the proto-Slavs of the Balkans.

The geneticist B. Sécher affirms that Yamnas migrated towards the lower Danube valley around 3.100 BC and one group went farther to the Balkans and formed the culture of Cernavoda. A second group formed the culture of Baden in Hungary and went farther up the Danube to Switzerland. A third group went quickly to Western Europe around 3.000 BC from Northern Italy to Southern France and the Iberian Peninsula. It was a people of seamen, horse-riders and metallurgists. It formed the Bell Beaker culture, present in Southern Europe from Hungary to Portugal via Northern Italy and Southern France, and spread this culture by sea along the Atlantic coast to the British Isles, bringing the civilisation of menhir-statues of Majkop, close to Yamna culture, and contributing to the megalithic civilisation which developed in Western Gaul and the British Isles, regions of Europe which gained at this time the strongest genetic concordance with Yamnas, who finished to build Stonehenge, taking the relay of farmers coming from Anatolia (who could stem from my point of view from Dravidians of Çatal Höyük or Göbekli Tepe) in 6.000 BC by the Iberian peninsula and the French Atlantic coast, according to Brace (2019). B. Sécher stresses that several archaeologists proposed to link the development of the Bell Beaker culture with the arrival of the first Celts in Western Europe, as they probably spoke a proto-Celtic language.

Several recent studies can also support the ancient theory of French historians, according to which Gauls stemmed from Cimmerians (**kymru** meaning compatriot in Gaulish) who would have come from Altay, Pamir or Hindu Kush to the Black Sea. Thracians, closely linked with Cimmerians, Illyrians, Sarmatians and Veneti would also originate from the North of the Black Sea. Around 5.000 BC, ancestors of Western Indo-Europeans, as Ligures (whose name could come from the Dravidian word *gori*, mountain) and Gauls, would have built an Empire in Ukraine, South-Eastern Russia, Moldova, Romania and Carpathian Mountains. The Gaulish tribe of Budyni even remained in the region of the river Don. All those peoples migrated farther, some of them to Poland (Veneti) others to Balkans (Thracians and Illyrians), others to Anatolia (Thracians, Illyrians, Veneti and Celts). Expelled from Anatolia, Cimmerians, Celts and Veneti migrated to Gaul. However, the Hallstatt and Urnfield civilisation expanded from the

Danubic region to Gaul only at the end of the Bronze Age, around 1.500 BC, which raises the question of the pertinence of the Kurgan theory to explain the origin of the megalithic civilisation which expanded in Gaul from around 5.000 BC, and this theory is therefore questioned.

1.2 Theories of earlier migrations

Many studies bring answers to the above-mentioned question, including Mallory’s (2001) study, mentioning migrations from Asia to Europe during the VIIth millennium BC and Skulj (2008) who explains the proximity between Sanskrit and archaic Slavic languages, as old Slavonic (linked to Old Bulgarian) and Slovenian by ancient contacts. This proximity, which extends to Gaulish, can be explained by the contribution to Gaulish of Veneti, ancestors of Slovenians, whose name would come from the Sanskrit word *vind*, known, familiar. Zaborowski (1904) underlines the close links of Veneti with Gauls from the birth of the civilisation of Halstatt, and then in Gaul, Northern Italy, Bohemia, Pannonia and Illyria, where Gauls were surrounded by Slavs and dissolved in the local population. Several Romanian studies underline the links of the Pelasgian Carpatho-Danubic civilisation with Vedic Indo-Aryans, older than the Kurgan culture, as well as between Dravidian, Caucasian, Romanian, Albanian, Etruscan and Iberian languages.

De Paniagua (1909) corroborates this theory, suggesting that Celts and Veneti would partly originate from Dravidians coming from primitive India, mixed with peoples of the steppes coming from Altay to settle in the first place in the Caucasus and the North of the Black Sea and form the civilisation of the Kurgans and migrate farther to the Danubic region and the Balkans, and then to Western Europe, where they would have brought the Dravidian megalithic civilisation. According to him, this theory is supported by the diffusion from India to the Caucasus, the Balkans, Italy and Brittany of the Dravidian words *vel*, *vin*, meaning white (*beli* in Slavic, **balaros**, **vindos** in Gaulish) and *kar*, *kara*, meaning black, which appear in the names of the white lake of Van in Armenia, the white Albania of the Caucasus and the Balkans, the Black Sea (*kara deniz* in Turkish), the black mountain of Montenegro (*crna gora* in Slavic), the Veneti of the Adriatic (whose name would come from the Dravidian word *adru*, area of water, as the name of the river Oder-Odra in Polish, where Veneti also settled), the white Venice and Vindobona (Vienna), the Carpathian mountains (black enclosure in Dravidian) and the white Valachia, the white Vannes and the black Carnac, the white Albion and the black Caledonia. The Celts would be “the Celestials of fire” in Dravidian and the Gauls “the Cocks”, from the Dravidian word *kur/kori/koli* which would have evolved in

Galli. According to the linguists Allan Bomhard and John Kern, these Dravidian migrants, whose first homeland would be Iran, and then the Indus valley, would have partly migrated to Central Siberia and could thus have mixed with the peoples of the steppes to migrate farther to the West. Bertrand (1884) also mentions this migration from the East, which could have brought the megalithic civilisation developed by Dravidians and built the menhirs of Carnac. The word druid would come from Dravidian, as well as the name of Zalmoxis, Thracian Grand Priester at the origin of Gaulish druidism. Brunaux (2008) also mentions the Indian origins of the Gaulish druidism.

2. EARLIER MIGRATIONS THEORIES SUPPORTED BY RECENT GENETIC AND ARCHAEOLOGICAL STUDIES

Fig.1, from National Geographic's (2011) *Genographic project* financed by IBM, gives a good summary of these migrations and the major role India

played in the spread of a civilisation coming from Eastern Africa to Southern Asia, the Central Asian steppes, Europe and Northern Africa. It supports the theory of a Dravidian migration from the Indus valley to Europe and to Middle and Near East to Northern Africa. It lacks however from my viewpoint migrations of steppe peoples between Altay and the present Uighur Region, where the Tocharian had settled, and the steppes of the North of the Caspian and Black Seas, as well as migrations between Iran, Anatolia and the Balkans, and between Iran, the Caucasus and the North of the Black Sea. These played a major role in the formation of Indo-European languages by creating a contact zone around the region of Zagros mountains in Western Iran. This region was linked with the Dravidian civilisation of the Indus valley to the East, and with Mesopotamia, Anatolia and the Caucasus to the West, as shown on Fig.2.

Figure 1. Out of Africa route (Source: Genographic Project website (2011), <http://www-03.ibm.com/press/us/en/photo/35881.wss>)

Figure 2. Mixed genetic origin of the first farmers in Europe (Source: the mixed genetic origin of the first farmers of Europe (2020), Biorxiv)

Fig.2 above clearly shows the contact zone between Zagros, Mesopotamia (Ubaid), Anatolia (Çatal Höyük, Göbekli Tepe), the Balkans (Vinča and other Balkan cultures of ancient Europe, including Butmir and Visoko) and Gaul (megaliths of 5.000 BC in Barnenez, Carnac, Gavrinis (Brittany) and in the Parisian basin, Glozel culture), as well as to Majkop (Northern Caucasus) and to Northern Gaul (Parisian basin) and Southern Gaul (Fontbouisse, Languedoc), French megalithic sites where can be found characteristic elements of the Ubaid and Majkop cultures according to Mosenkis' study *Dravidian Çatal Höyük, Ubaid, Balkan and West European Neolithic priest elite*, stressing links between Dravidians and the Balkan and West European Neolithic clergy, as Vinča's cult language could be Dravidian, given the Dravidian etymology of several words of the Vinča script.

Perdih's (2018) study, on links between the spread of languages and the spread of haplogroups G2a, R1a et R1b, as shown below on Fig. 3, 4 and 5, also confirms migrations between the Indus region, Mesopotamia, Anatolia, the Balkans, Gaul and the British Isles, as well as to Egypt, Northern Africa du Nord

and the Iberian Peninsula at coherent dates with the spread of the megalithic culture and the formation of the Balkan culture, disproving the theory of a spread of this culture to the East. Quiles' (2018) study strengthens Perdih's theory by mentioning the spread of haplogroups R2 M479 (Dravidian, Kartvelian and Uralian) in Iberia, R1a M420 (Indo-Uralian) and R1b M343 (present in particular in Zagros) in Southern France, which pleads from his viewpoint for a migration to Europe by the South. Hay's (2017) study confirms that Neolithic farmers coming from Anatolia via the Balkans also brought haplogroups H and J1c, characteristic of Dravidians, as in particular H1 and H2, highly present among the Dravidians, which spread to Hungary and the Balkans and were also found in Gaul according to the Y-Chromosome STR Haplotype Reference Database (YHRD, (<https://yhrd.org/>)) confirming ancient links. Rivollat's (2016) thesis confirms that haplogroups G2a, N1a, K1a, T et H spread in Gaul in the Neolithic from the regions of Pakistan, Iran, Anatolia, the Caucasus and the Balkans from where they came.

Figure 3. Map of the spread of haplogroup G2a according to Anton Perdi (2018)

Figure 4. Map of the spread of haplogroup R1b according to Anton Perdi (2018)

Figure 5. Map of the spread of haplogroup R1a according to Anton Perdi (2018)

tral Asia, Anatolia, the Caucasus and Europe haplogroups stemming from India as Y-DNA G M-201, H M-52, R1a M-17, R2 M-124, K M-9, L M-20, J2b2... His dating of the latest migration is supported by the presence of haplogroup R1b in Villabruna in 14.000 BP, coherent with Arya's (2019) dating a migration of Danaans from India to Greece in 13.000 BC.

Figure 7. Map of migrations from Indus region to West between 15000 BP and 10.000 BP (according to Narendra Katkar 2011)

Heyer (2020 and 2008) also mention three waves of East-West migrations in Eurasia from the Aurignacian, bringing Venus statues as the Venus of Lespugues, and underline the major role of Central Asia in these migrations and in the expansion of haplogroup R and Central-Asian languages. Heyer also underlines the genetic proximity of Pamirian Tajiks with Europeans. The presence in Europe of old Indian haplogroups C and F Y-DNA and M and U2 mt-DNA already at the Aurignacian also tends to strengthen these theories. Rondu (2021) states that a migration at the Gravettian, which already brought haplogroup R1b to Europe, is at the origin of the pyramids of Visoko in Bosnia and Herzegovina. According to the Authentic Gatha Zoroastrianism (2018) study, these ancient migrations also brought to Europe haplogroups I M-170 and I P-215, among the most ancient European haplogroups, present in France from the Aurignacian, haplogroups of 80% of the Iranian Zoroastrian priests, found in megalithic tombs in Europe, who would have brought their religion. These conclusions are corroborated by Horvath (2021), stating that haplogroup I originated in Central Asia, as Burushaski and Dravidian, as well as by Borsboom (2020). Haplogroup I was present in Zagros.

Dupanloup et al. (2004) confirm that a large scale migration of Neolithic farmers took place from Anatolia to all Europe from 8.000 BC, bringing a significant part of the European genome (from 20% in the British Isles to 30% in France and 75% in the Balkans), mainly Anatolian (50% in mean) and Basque (more than 35% in mean, almost 50% in France) and to a lesser extent Northern African or North-Eastern Asian, the latter being confined to Eastern Europe and Finland. This migration could also contribute to the spread of the Dravidian language, about which Cavalli-Sforza (1988) underlines that Dravidian was spoken originally from Minor Asia to the Middle East, Iran and India, and could therefore be spread by Neolithic farmers to the Balkans and Gaul from 8.000 BC and contribute to the formation of Indo-European languages. This is attested by the spread from the Caucasus to Southern Gaul and the Iberian Peninsula, along with Basque genes attested by the above-mentioned studies, of Ibero-Caucasian languages, which have numerous linguistic concordances with Dravidian and gave birth to Iberian languages and Basque.

Rondu (2017) attests of the diffusion to Europe of the civilisation of pastoralism for milk from the Iranian Zagros mountains and the Caucasus from 7.000 BC (see Fig. 8). These brought haplogroups Mt-DNA H2a and H2a1, specific of South-Caucasus, along with haplogroups Y-DNA R1a M-417, R1a M-420, R1a M-458, R1a Z-282 and Z-93, R1b M-343, R1b M-415, R1b-V88, L1a, J1-M267, J2a et J2b, which Rondu partly links with a proto-Dravidian migration to South-Caucasus around 8.500 BC, attested in particular by the presence of the proto-Dravidian haplogroup L1/LM-20 in South-Caucasus. Fig. 9 shows the expansion of haplogroup L from India to the Caucasus, Anatolia, and Southern Europe. Rondu supports his thesis by the diffusion of toponyms van, vand (forest, mountain, water area in Dravidian), pand (linked to shepherds, God Pan and cheese-making and the Tamil king Pandion of the Black Sea) and don (river, which I link to Dravidian tundna, pour water, and the Vedic Goddess of water Dana) from India to Spain and Portugal, the cult of the tree of Gilan region (in Northern Iran, called then Hyrcania, evoking the Gaulish Hercynian forest), the diffusion of Venus statues as the Venus of Brassempouy and megalithism. He underlines the major role of South-Caucasus in the spread of these haplogroups in Europe, as in the Steppes of Ural and Volga.

Figure 8. Diffusion of Mt-DNA haplogroups H2a and H2a1 (source: Google Earth/Family tree DNA/M-O, Rondu 2017)

Figure 9. Map of diffusion of haplogroup L (Source: E. Chernoff 2017)

The Oxford handbook of Ancient Anatolia (2012) also refers to the Neolithic expanded to Anatolia from the North-West of Iran and links it to the Zarzian culture of Zagros Mountains, which developed from the late Pleistocene. The Iranian scholar Shahmiri, in his (2020) study Volcae (Golestan, South East of Caspian Sea), the original land of Celtic people, underlines the links between Gilaki/Galeshi peoples and Gauls, considering that Gauls originated in the South Caspian region of Golistan, and provides archeological, religious and linguistic evidence to support this theory as the name of several Gaulish tribes as Senoni, Atrebatii and Volcae. Shahmiri (2020) mentions in

support of his theory that these peoples originated from the forested mountain of Hyrcania, also called Golistan, that, according to ancient Akkadian sources, there was a forest called Arqania in the South of the Caucasus. In fact, according to ancient Greek sources, a land called Hyrcanis in Lydia, that Strabo mentioned a migration from Hyrcania, and Pliny mentioned the wooded mountains of Hercynium in Dacia and Hyrcani in Macedonia, besides the Hercynian forest in Germany, to which I add the region of Quercy in Gaul, all are related to perkunyo, wooded mountain in Celtic, and the Dravidian word perkuni, meaning grow for trees. Here I notice the similarity of

the Celtic religious feast of Beltane and the Gilaki religious feast of Bal Novruz. As shown in Fig. 10 below, there are similar mouthless statues-menhirs in the South-Caspian region and in Gaul. I could also find in Shahmiri's studies similarities between Elamite and Gilaki languages and Gaulish, supported by *The Gilaki language* (2012), from Uppsala University.

Several genetic studies clearly show that haplogroup R1b, et and in particular the European haplogroup R1b M-269, characteristic of Celts, migrated from Southern Siberia to North-Western China, where Tocharian settled, N-W Pakistan and India, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Iran, Armenia, the Caucasus, Anatolia, the Balkans and Western Europe, as shown on Fig. 11 below, published by the geneticist M. Hay on Eupedia. Fig. 12 below shows that this haplogroup is present at a high frequency of 20-

40% from the Caspian Sea to Assyria, Armenia and Syria, which tends to give credit to the questioned existence of a Celtic language in this region, Euphratic. These data corroborate Dogan et al. (2017) study, Syriacs bearing 30% of R1b.

The theory of the Indo-Iranian origin of the Celts is also supported by Talageri (2020), stating that one of the most Western Rigvedic tribes, the Druhyus, settled in Northern Pakistan, migrated early to Afghanistan, the Caspian region and then Gaul, bringing the Celtic religion, which he considers as the closest to the Vedic religion, this tribe giving its name to the word druid in Gaulish, but also to the word drug, friend in Slavic. This migration could be linked to the dispersion of Burushaski, linked to the Anus tribe of the same region, who also migrated towards West, after being defeated around 8.500 BC.

Fig. 10. Expansion of megalithism from Iran to Gaul (source: Shahmiri 2020)

Figure 11. Map of repartition of haplogroup R1b. (Source Maciamo Hay 2014, Eupedia)

Figure 12. High levels of haplogroup R1b M-269 from Iran to Syria (David Reich lecture 9 February 2015 - Page 42, *Anthrogenica*; <https://anthrogenica.com/showthread.php?3807-David-Reich-lecture-9-February-2015/page-42>)

Szecsényi-Nagy’s (2015) interesting study about the genome of Neolithic Carpatho-Danubians published by Mainz University, clearly shows that the genome of this population is closely linked to Anatolia,

the Caucasus, Syria, Iraq, Iran, and further East to Afghanistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Pakistan, as shown on Fig.13 below. She also underlines genetic links between archaic Balkan and French peoples, including Basques.

Figure 13. Genome similarities (according to Anna Szecsényi-Nagy 2015)

The map of the diffusion of haplogroup R1b presented in Fig. 14, published on indo-european.eu, confirms that this haplogroup spread from Siberia to North-Western China, Central Asia, Iran, the Caucasus, Anatolia, the Balkans and Western Europe. According to Horvath (2021) haplogroup R stemmed from haplogroup P1, which came around 29.000 BCE

from Insular South-East Asia to Eastern Siberia and Central Asia, where this haplogroup is still found at quite high frequencies (28% in Altay, 17% by Uighurs, 10% by Turkmens and 9% in Northern Iran), which tends to support a Southern migration of haplogroup R1b.

Figure 14. Diffusion of haplogroup R1b. (Source: indo-european.eu, Quilès 2019)

The pioneer of prehistoric archaeology, Gordon Clyde, already mentioned in the 30's the migration of a pastoral Alpine culture, characterised by goat-breeding and the culture of rye, from the Himalayas to the Zagros, the Caucasus, Anatolia, the Balkans and the Alps, as shown on the map in Fig. 15.

The North-Western Indian origin of main haplogroups is underlined by Van Driem (2014) as shown on Fig. 16 (a,b).

Figure 15. Map of diffusion of Europeans (from Brami 2019)

Figure 16. A prehistoric thoroughfare from the Ganges to the Himalayas (a, b maps of diffusion of main Haplogroups (according to George Van Driem 2014)

Menon (2019) supports, on the basis of many recent genetical discoveries and the dispersion of agriculture from India, the theory of a migration coming from the Indus valley, homeland of Dravidians, to Zagros mountains in Iran around 7700/7400 BC, then around 6250 BC to the Volga region, the Caucasus and Anatolia, and then to the Balkans and Western Europe. R. Menon mentions the arrival in Iberia (El Trocs, Pyrénées) around 5.100 BC of the haplogroup R1a1a, underlining its Indian, and particularly Dravidian, origin (NB: it would be in fact the haplogroup R1b1, the presence in El-Trocs of the haplogroup J1c3 supporting its Dravidian origin), and the genetical analysis of goats dated from 5000 BC in France, attesting that one of them stemmed from Pakistan and the second from Central Asia through the North of the Black Sea. According to him, this migration gave also birth to the megalithic civilisation of Majkop in North Caucasus.

Herbo (2017) underlines that this culture spread to France, where similar objects to the Ubaid and Indian culture were discovered, as for instance in Glozel, Allier, a phallic bisexual symbol similar to the Vedic linga-yoni and statuettes of a Fish-God - avatar of Vishnu in the Vedic religion - similar to those of Vinča and dated from 5000 BC. Yet thermoluminescence dating proved that they were made around 2000 years ago and remixed of broken pieces during Medieval times (McKerrell et al., 1975; Liritzis 1997).

Also, pre-Celtic engraved tablets similar to the Indus script according to Schildmann (1999), in which this expert of ancient languages, including Sumerian and the Indus script, which he deciphered, underlines concordances between the Indus script, ancient scripts of the Balkans and scripts of the megalithic civilisation up to Brittany (Carnac, Gavrinis). As an example of these links, the caduceus symbol spread

from India to Sumer, Anatolia and Gavrinis. The links between these ancient scripts are corroborated by Friedrich (2007), underlining close similarities of Glozel signs, dated from 2.500 BC, with scripts of Vinča, the pyramids of Visoko (Bosnia), Sumer (Ubaid) and the Mas d'Azil (Ariège, France). This supports the theory of this ancient migration, as well as similarities stressed by De Benoist (1997) between the scripts of Vinča and the Indus valley.

Several other studies also tend to corroborate the Out of India theory. Marcantonio and Nath Jha's (2013) underline the links of early Indo-European with Vedic Sanskrit and other Indian languages as Dravidian and Austronesian languages, Western Asian languages as Mitanni and Caucasian languages. Elst's (2015) study underlines the Indian origin of Indo-European and placing their homeland in North-Western India. Borsboom's (2020) interesting theory supported by many genetical and archaeological data, postulates that seafarers from Pakistan and North-Western India settled in all European coastal lands bringing the ancient European haplogroup I, supporting the Mediterranean route mentioned on Brami's map. Priyadarshi (2017) interesting study postulates that domestic mice began to migrate with agriculture from India between 15.000 and 10.000 BC to Iran, Anatolia and France.

3. THE HISTORY OF GAULS ALSO ATTESTS OF THESE ANCIENT MIGRATIONS

Recent studies corroborate Thierry (1828) who already mentioned a Cimmerian migration from Taurid Chersonese to the Danube, Gaul, and then Wales. According to him, Cimmerians occupied in Gaul, around 500 BC, a territory bordered by the line of the Seine and the Marne in the North, the Saône in the East, the Garonne in the South and the Atlantic in the

West. They founded a confederation around the Armorican confederation, led by Veneti, including Nanneti (Loire Atlantique), Coriosoliti, Ostimii (Finistère), Redoni (Rennes), Abrincati and Uxelli (Cotentin), Baiocassi and Lexovii (Calvados), to which joined Andi (maybe linked to Anti, Slavic people of the region of the Don, the Dnieper and the Black Sea), Turoni, Carnuti, Senoni (Yonne), Lingoni (from the plateau of Langres, whose name could come from *linga*, Dravidian phallic religious symbol), Cenomani, Aulerci (including a tribe settled in Avallon, Brannovici, whose name attests of a Slavic origin), Petrocorii, Santoni (Saintonge), Pictoni (Poitou), and Lemovici (Limousin). A. Thierry also mentions among Cimmerians Boii or Boghi (whose name would come from the Cimmerian bug, terrible, linked to Bog, God in Slavic), of whom several tribes settled in Gaul and who founded in Bohemia a Cimmerian confederation. A second wave of Cimmerians would have settled around 300 BC on a territory bordered by the Seine, the Marne, the Vosges, the Rhine, the North Sea and present Belgium, including Leuci (Lemks?), Mediomatrici (Moselle), Remi (Reims), Suessoni (Soisson), Bellovaci (Beauvais), Caleti (pays de Caux), Ambiani (Somme), Atrebatii (Artois), Morini (Boulonnais). It is interesting to note that this list partly matches with the list of Slavic peoples mentioned in Serafimov (2010), and that Atrebatii (linked to *trem*, village in old Slavic) and Ambiani (linked to *oba*, both in Slavic) also bear Slavic sounding names. According to A. Thierry, Cimmerians are at the origin of druidism in Gaul and England, introduced by the Priest Hu, Heus or Hesus, surnamed the powerful, who led the first Cimmerian invasion. A. Thierry also mentions Ligures or Ligors, who preceded the Gauls in Gaul, whose name would derive from the Slavic *gora* as they came from a chain of mountains. He also specifies that the Gauls, in their migrations to the Danube and Illyria, mixed with Sarmatian and Cimmerian peoples as Bastarni and are at the origin of Gallo-Illyrian peoples as Scordisci, Iapodi, Carni and Taurisci.

As a fact, Gauls (including Senoni and Boii), migrated to Italy and the Balkans already in 587 BC, after the first sack of Rome, and again from Italy to Danubic Europe and the Balkans around 300 BC where, under the name of Scordisci, they created a federation with Sarmatian-speaking Pannonian and Illyrian peoples, named by various historians Illyrian Gaul, and migrated farther to Macedonia and Greece. After their defeat in Delphi in 279 BC, some came back to Gaul, others settled in Thrace or Anatolian Galatia, and others came back to the region situated between the Sava and the Danube where they came from, with Singidunum (present Belgrade) as capital, from the name

of the Syginni, Thraco-Cimmerian people coming from the Volga. A Serbian study underlines the close proximity of Serbs, whose name would come from Sarmatian, with Sarmatians-Scythians-Veneti, whom they would have followed from the Black Sea to the Balkans and with whom they would have shared the same runic alphabet. Pouqueville (1839) states that Illyrians also spoke a proto-Slavic language, although not much is known about it. These migrations gave the Gauls an opportunity to mix up with proto-Slavic peoples who could influence the Gaulish language. Boii, coming from Bohemia, also opened outposts in Silesia, Polish-Ukrainian Galicia and Transylvania.

Thierry's analysis matches with Serafimov (2010) who points that the name of various Gaulish tribes, numerous geographic toponyms and names of Gods stem from Slavic. P. Serafimov mentions several Boii peoples settled in Gaul, Aedui (linked to the Thracian tribe Aedii), Bituriges Cubi (from *turg*, *trg*, market and *kupiti*, buy), whose Slavic origin is supported by the name of their most famous Chief, Belovesus, who led the Gaulish attack on Rome in 587 BC, Volcae Tectosagi from Toulouse, one of the Galatian tribes of Anatolia (from *volk*, wolf), Cabali (from *kovali*, blacksmith), Petrogorii (linked with *vetrogorji*, windy hills by the Atlantic), Belovaci (from *bel*, white, *ves*, village), Lemovici (linked to Ukrainian Lemks), Nervii (linked to Ukrainian Neuri), Ostimii (from *ostatni*, last, as they lived at the West end of Gaul), Saluvii (from *slavuj*, famous), Velavii (from *Velavji*, valuable men), Segusiavii (from *sekati*, cut, *sejati*, sow), Mandubii, Meduli (from *med*, honey), Cadurci, Santoni, Ruthenians, Veneti. He also mentions the presence of numerous Slavic toponyms in Gaul, including 300 in Brittany, giving credit to the Slavic origin of Veneti, and God names as Baco, revered in Chalon sur Saône, linked to Bhaga, Dravidian God, Bago in Scythian, Bog, God in Slavic. He mentions linguistic similarities between Gaulish, Scythian, Thraco-Cimmerian and links between Slovenians, Veneti, Etruscans and Gauls and underlines that, according to Diodorus Siculus, the Cimmerians migrated from Asia to the Atlantic and Northern European seas. He specifies that, according to Herodotus and Hippolytus, the Grand Priest of the Thracian tribe Getae, Zalmoxis, surnamed the Scythian, was at the origin of Gaulish druidism, as attested by the Thracian etymology of the word druid. P. Serafimov links the word Scythian with *skitati se* (wander in Bosnian). He concludes from the linguistic similarities between Gaulish, Scythian and Thracian that contacts of Gauls with proto-Slavs are very ancient.

Martin (1752) already came to this conclusion, mentioning ancient links between Gauls, Thracians

and Illyrians, ancient migrations of Bebryci, Bithynian Thracians, and Colchian Argonauts in Gaul from the Cimmerian country and the first expedition of Segevesus in Illyria in 587 BC. Sergent (1988) supports this thesis, mentioning the arrival of three Celtic tribes in 800 BC in Anatolian Thrace by the Balkans from the region of Hallstatt, Dolioni, Mariandyni and Bebryci, whose name is close to Bibracte, capital of the Aedui, and Bebryci, a Pyrenean tribe. He also mentions the Celtic origin of Edoni, a Thracian tribe which name reminds the Aedui's name, and the presence of Cimmerians and Veneti in Anatolia. Did the Aedui, settled in my ancestral Morvan, who prouided themselves of their Trojan origins by the Romans, really come from the Trojan region where these Celtic tribes lived? I finally also noticed that several tribe names (Petrogorii, from *Rocky Mountains*, Mandubii, *cattle herders* from Auxois, Velavii, *valorous men*, Caleti, from *kali*, hero), have a credible Dravidian etymology.

Serafimov (2014) also mentions the similarity of religious and funeral rituals, as well as architecture, between Gauls and the Balkan Slavs and the importance of metal work for these peoples. For instance, the Stećci brought in Bosnia and Herzegovina by the Vlasi, descendants of the Scordisci, of Gaulish origin, according to Leopold Contzen, who names them Stari Vlasi (old Gauls), remind the menhirs of Brittany, which isn't astonishing given the already mentioned migrations, and the treasure of Vix, in the Burgundy of my ancestors, would be of Venetian origin, Vix being on the road of metals controlled by Veneti.

Du Buat-Nançay (1772) in addition also notes that, among the main peoples who took part in Gaulish expeditions, Senoni would stem from Cimmerians, Volcae or Volgae Tectosagi would stem from Sacians from the Don-Volga, close to Scythians et Sarmatians, as Boii, who would stem from the Dacians Parni, a Saccian tribe speaking a language close to Sarmatian, belonging to the Illyrian Scordisci who took part in the creation of Northern Galatia on the banks of the Don near Scythians. The name Boii also reminds the name of Bojki, a mountain tribe, mix of Vlasi and Ruthenians, from Ukraine and Poland.

Numerous studies also underline the major role of Veneti, by their migration from the region of the Don and the Dniester to Thrace, the Balkans, Austria, Germany, Gaul, and then the British Isles, as well as of the Carni and Illyrians who came with them, in the proximity between Gaulish and Celtic languages and the Slavic languages of the Balkans. Certain researchers even establish a link between the Gaulish Carnuti and the Slovenian Carni, whom Contzen (1861) presents as Gaulish. In the reverse direction, a Serbian study underlines the importance of Senoni in the diffusion of the Celtic language by their migrations to the Balkans, and in particular to the present Bosnia

and-Herzegovina, suggesting that they would have given their name to the Sana, which is credible given that L. Contzen clearly presents the Scordisci as stemming from the Gauls who took part in the sack of Rome, to which Senoni took part, and places their settlement in present-day Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina. Several other sources also mention the migration of Senoni from the region of Ancona, in Italy, where Adriatic Veneti had also settled, to the Balkans, Greece, and then Galatia, where the Senon Brennus of the Gaulish attack on Delphs, who would not have been killed in the end, would have gone on the invitation of the King of Bithynia. This Serbian study also evokes the role of the Vlasi, Celts coming from the West, in the diffusion of the Celtic culture, in particular in present Bosnia and Herzegovina. It also underlines the role of other peoples on this linguistic proximity, as Ruthenians, who have migrated to Gaul according to Caesar, and Boii, migrating from the region of the Danube, where Gauls had also settled around Bratislava at about 300 BC and were therefore in contact with them, to Gaul, where Boii settled under the protection of Aedui, with whom they were closely linked, between the rivers Loire and Allier after the battle of Bibracte in the Morvan of my ancestors. The localisation of the oppidum of Boii, Gergovie, is still disputed, but according to several sources it could be situated near my family house in the Nièvre, in Saint Révérien, Saint Pierre le Moutier or Saint Parize le Châtel, or maybe in Sancerre, in the Cher, this last hypothesis being however considered as less credible by the authors of a study on the Aedui.

Considering these studies, it seems credible that the Gauls came from around the Black Sea where, coming from Central Asia, had settled, between Ukraine, Colchis, Anatolia and Thrace, Cimmerians, Celts, Dravidians and nomads as Scythians, Thracians, Sarmatians and Sacians, with whom Celts and Cimmerians were closely linked, which is corroborated in particular by linguistic similarities between Gaulish, Thracian and Bulgarian.

Certain scholars, as F. Pouqueville, consider that Celtic and Slavic peoples would have melt in one. Celt and Slav would come from the same word, *clavo* or *slava*, glory, and the Senoni would have given their first king to the Slavs, Samo, who united the Slavs from Lusatia to Slovenia. Asterix would thus be a little Bosnian...

4. LINGUISTIC STUDY

4.1. *Lexical concordances*

Serafimov (2014) shows that Gaulish is the most similar Celtic language with Slavic languages, which is logical given the very ancient and close links between Gauls and the proto-Slavic world, attested by

these studies. It shows in particular the proximity of Gaulish with Slavic languages of the Balkans, as Bulgarian and Slovenian, to which I would add Bosnian-Serbian-Croatian-Montenegrin (BSCM) and Czech. On the basis of Gaulish dictionaries as Savignac (2004) and Serafimov's study, I found 500 Gaulish words linked with Slavic (including 400 with BSCM), that is around half of identified Gaulish words. Moreover, I could find the etymologies of these words and establish that 250 words show concordances with Dravidian and 160 words with Burushaski on the basis of Burrow-Emeneau's (1984) and Caldwell's (1856) Dravidian dictionaries and Casule's (2017) Burushaski dictionary. One can find these common roots in APPENDIX 1.

4.2. Grammatical concordances

Apart from lexical concordances, basing on Piqueron (2015), Gaulish shares with Slavic many grammatical concordances. There are three genders of words in Gaulish, masculine, feminine and neutral, as in Slavic. Both are flexional with similar cases. There are imperfective and perfective verbs in Gaulish as in Slavic, and the conjugation of verbs and the formation of participles show similarities as for instance auxiliaries to form the future *byu*, which can be related to *budu* in Russian, *bivaju*, I will be in BSCM, and *syu*, similar to *ću* in BSCM, as there are two forms of future in Gaulish as in Slavic languages, in particular of the Balkan. There is no verb "to have" in Gaulish, replaced by "to me is" (dative), as in Russian. Personal pronouns, possessive adjectives and prepositions are similar in Gaulish, Slavic, Dravidian and Burushaski.

Tonoyan-Belyayev (2020) underlines that Dravidian and Indo-European are the only two Eurasiatic language families possessing a system of three grammatical genders, masculine, feminine and neutral, as Slavic and Gaulish. They also have a similar vowel system, similar declinations with nominative, accusative, genitive, instrumental and locative, similar pronouns, a similar formation of plural, similar verb systems, in particular to form present participle, future and past tense with participle. He underlines in particular that Dravidian shares with Celtic and Italic a very similar suffix *b* to form the future. He considers that some of these features are shared with Turkic, which tend to give credit to my theory that Dravidian expanded to Anatolia and Central Asia. He also mentions lexical similarities between Dravidian and Indo-European languages. As concerns the timing, he proposes to place the Sprachbund or split of a deeper macrofamily in Neolithic times, some one-to-two millennia before the beginning of Early Bronze Age in some most ancient regions (that is between 5.500 and

4.500 BC, or probably a bit earlier). He proposes to place the common *Urheimat* in a territory around the Indus-Sarasvati valley and South-Eastern Iran. He underlines that in that epoch no separate IE languages existed, all Proto-IE dialects not differing much from each other and looking and sounding mostly similar to the correct results of PIE reconstructions. First, common IE and common Dravidian separated, Dravidian went into Central and Southern India, then IE began to split, most Dravidian speakers went out from South Asia. I can mostly agree with his theory. However, as I believe that some proto-Dravidians also migrated to the Caucasus, Anatolia, the Balkans and Western Europe, I would place the formation of this common Sprachbund earlier, around 8.500 BC, to make it fit with the expansion of agriculture from Anatolia 8.000 to 9.500 years ago, the formation of the civilisation of Vinča around 6.000 years BC and the formation of the Megalithic civilisation in Gaul around 5.000 BC. I would also extend the *Urheimat* to Zagros and the Caspian Sea region which played a major role, as the Celtic haplogroup R1b-M343 would have originated from this region according to above-mentioned studies.

Swaminatha Aiyar (1987) also pinpoints lexical and grammatical concordances between Dravidian languages, Sanskrit, Avestan and other Indo-European languages. I could find in this study striking similarities between Dravidian and Bosnian demonstrative pronouns, which both share the rare characteristic of having three different forms according to the distance (close, intermediate and far). Dravidian, Burushaski and BSCM also share an interrogative mode using the prefix *da*. This study also underlines similarities between Dravidian and Balto-Slavic as concerns the causative mode, expressed in Tamil by the suffix *pi*, similar to the Slavic conditional suffix *bi*. I found other similarities in suffixes and prefixes, as well as in verb endings between Dravidian, Slavic languages and Gaulish. Moreover, I could find in this book many words quoted in my study, and a few others, corroborating lexical concordances between these languages. Other grammatical concordances can also be found between French, Slavic and Burushaski.

4.3. Linguistic comments

My conclusions are in line to a large extent with those of Meier-Brugger (2013) reference book underlining that "*Celtic, coming from the Yamna culture, last stage of the linguistic unity, has ancient links with Eastern Indo-European, from which came Greek, Phrygian, Indo-Iranian and Slavic, and in particular with South-Carpathian languages as Thracian, Illyrian, Slavic languages of the Balkans, Ukrainian and North-Caucasian languages dating as long ago as the Vth millennium BC*". They are

also in line with Schmidt (2007) showing ancient links between Celtic and Eastern Indo-European (Indo-Iranian, Balto-Slavic, Phrygian, Greek, Albanian, Armenian) and Georgian. Pellard et al., (2018) mentions in this respect, on the basis of Bird's (1982) study, 601 Celto-Greek roots, 523 Celto-Indo-Iranian roots, 703 Celto-Germanic roots and 554 Celto-Baltic roots, that is more than the 546 Celto-Italic roots. K-H. Schmidt gives examples of concordances between Celtic and Eastern Indo-European languages, absent between Celtic and Italic, which leads him to question the pertinence of placing Celtic in the Western Indo-European branch. M. Meier-Brugger, as K-H. Schmidt, questions therefore the frequently employed notion of Italo-Celtic languages, underlining that there was no initial Italo-Celtic stage and that contacts between Celtic and Italic are more recent, placing Celtic with Germanic and Balto-Slavic. As a fact, my study shows that, when there are several Indo-European roots, Gaulish took over the same roots as Slavic (for instance *lubi* for love and *boglo*, *od* for water, whereas French took over later the Indo-European roots *amajo* and *aqa*). The influence of Germanic on Gaulish also appeared later as at first Gaulish, as the dominant language, influenced the formation of Germanic, before the latter took over the ascendent when the Gaulish power regressed. Cimmerians would be by the way the ancestors, not only of Gauls, but also of Cimbri and Sicambri, and thus of Franks. Some researchers also consider them also as the ancestors of Slavs, or at least as closely linked to Ukrainian proto-Slavs as the Neuri. Hamp (2013) places Cimmerian in an Indo-European branch including Germanic, Balto-Slavic languages, pre-Hellenic, Thracian, Dacian, Illyrian, Albanian and Messapian. Beckwith (2009) places Celtic with Baltic, Slavic, Albanian and Iranian. M. Gimbutas links Celts with Germans, Balto-Slavs, Phrygians and Illyrians and Indo-Iranians via the Andronovo culture. The convergence of all these analyses give credit to links between Celtic and Slavic.

It also clearly appears that a significant part of Gaulish roots linked to Slavic stem from Indo-European, Sanskrit, Dravidian and Burushaski. A. Bomhard places the original homeland of Nostratic languages (Indo-European, Dravidian, Altaic, Kartvelian) in the South of Caucasus, around 8.000 BC, from where these languages would have spread to the homeland of the Indo-European language acknowledged by many researchers, from the Caucasus to the North of the Black Sea. The striking linguistic concordances which I could notice between Gaulish, Slavic, Dravidian, Altaic and Kartvelian in Bomhard (2018) and in Dravidian dictionaries as that of Burrow-Emeneau (1984) plead for a common original homeland. According to *the Cambridge handbook of ar-*

east linguistic (2017), Dravidian is at the origin of Sanskrit and Indo-Iranian languages. These concordances can also be explained by the influence of Cimmerians, who came from Altay, Pamir or Hindu Kush and had attested links with Indo-Iranians.

4.4. Dravidian, Burushaski, French and Slavic languages

Although it exceeds the strict frame of this study, the influence of Dravidian, and to a lesser degree Burushaski, not only on Gaulish, but also on French and Slavic languages, seems to me worth to be mentioned. Beside the already mentioned linguistic correspondences, other similarities are worth mentioning between modern French and Dravidian, some of them also extending to English (APPENDIX 2).

Numerous words of Dravidian origin can also be found in Kartvelian, as *cikni*, small, linked to *cikni*, small in Burushaski, *cikka*, small child in Dravidian, which could give *chico* in Spanish, *laparaki*, speak, from *laba*, *paray*, speak in Dravidian, *laau*, *baret* in Burushaski, which could give *labaraio*, speak in Gaulish, and *palabre* in French, or *taj*, mother in Dravidian, which could give *da*, mother in Georgian, and *dea*, women in Gaulish.

Numerous correspondences with Scythian languages, and in particular Finno-Ugrian languages, confirming that Dravidians were in contact with the peoples of the Siberian steppes are found in Caldwell (1856). There he considers that globally Dravidian is closer to Western Indo-European languages than to Sanskrit, which attests from his point of view of older and closer contacts with these languages than with Sanskrit.

Devanayan (2001), writing about Tamil, also mentions a Dravidian migration to Mesopotamia, Egypt and North Africa, as well as to Anatolia and Western Europe. G. Devanayan bases his theory partly on Lahovary (1963) linking Dravidians with the Mediterranean pre-Indo-European culture, and in particular with Basques and Kartvelian, and placing their original homeland in Mesopotamia. G. Devanayan considers however that Dravidians came from India. He gives numerous examples of linguistic correspondences attesting of close links of Dravidian with Anglo-Saxon and Germanic languages, but also with French, which I limited to the most convincing.

I was able to inventory 250 words of Dravidian origin in Gaulish and 160 words of Burushaski, respectively one half and around one third of Gaulish words close to Slavic, and even 100 words of Dravidian origin in French, which attests of these close links.

Even the name of my ancestral Morvan can come from Dravidian *mara*, dark and *vanam*, holy wooded mountain, this correspondence being even more

striking with the name of the oppidum of Morvennum, and the Aedui people' name - from **aidwos**, ardent - settled in Morvan would come from Dravidian **odi**, heat.

This strengthens the hypothesis of a Dravidian migration from 8.500 BC, which would have passed through the Caucasus, the north of the Black Sea and Anatolia towards the Balkans, Italy and Gaul, and of close contacts between Gauls and Dravidians, which left traces even in French, as linguistic correspondences are confirmed by genetical, archaeological, historical and religious data. Numerous researchers underline in this respect the links between the Balkan cultures of "ancient Europe" with the Dravidian culture of the Indus valley.

5. DISCUSSION

This interdisciplinary study, based on linguistic, genetic, historical, archaeological, agricultural and religious data, strengthens the theory of a peopling of Europe from N-W India, Pakistan, Iran, the Caucasus and Anatolia. This has created a proto-Indo-Mediterranean culture, relativizing the importance of the Kurgan theory for the peopling of Europe, which would however have later brought 28% of the French genome according to Brunel's (2020).

It also gives credibility to the linguistic matches I establish between Gaulish, Slavic, Dravidian and Burushaski (250 Dravidian and 160 Burushaski words out of 500 Gaulish/Slavic words). In fact, Bouckaert et al. (2012) tends to strengthen my theory. It states that there are two competing hypotheses for the origin of the Indo-European language family. The conventional view places the homeland in the Pontic steppes about 6000 years ago. An alternative hypothesis claims that these languages spread from Anatolia with the expansion of farming 8000 to 9500 years ago. Using Bayesian phylogeographic approaches and basic vocabulary data from 103 old and contemporary Indo-European languages to model the expansion of the family and test these hypotheses, this study concludes in a decisive support to an Anatolian origin over a steppe origin, as both the inferred timing and root location of the Indo-European language trees fit with an agricultural expansion from Anatolia beginning 8000 to 9500 years ago. A map from this study places the origin of Indo-Iranian languages between N-W India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, the Caspian Sea and Zagros, which I consider as the original homeland of Dravidian and Indo-European languages, and shows close links between Indo-Iranian, Caucasian and Anatolian languages. This pleads for a formation of Indo-European languages in this region before 8.000 BC, as stated in this study.

The formation of Indo-European in this region could be also attested by the interesting Burushaski language of Northern Pakistan which, according to Witzel (2012) mixes features from Dravidian, Sanskrit and Caucasian languages and shares the vigesimal numeration with Dravidian, Caucasian and Basque, which left traces in French (*vimsati*, twenty in Dravidian, could even have given *vingt*, twenty in French). Greenhill's (2012) interesting study places Burushaski between Kannada, a Dravidian language, Hindi, Caucasian languages and Basque, which supports its archaic character. The Ukrainian linguist I. Mosenkis also underlines the links of Burushaski, which he considers as very archaic, with Sino-Caucasian and Indo-European languages as Armenian, Phrygian and paleo-Balkan languages. Boc et al.'s (2010) interesting study reinforces the links between Celtic and Indo-Iranian languages, Slavic and Indo-Iranian languages, as well as between Slavic and Celtic languages. Boc et al., consider that this may be the evidence of a much closer common ancestry between these clusters than generally thought or of an intensive migration of the ancestors of the involved nations.

Interestingly, Bouckaert et al. (2012) places the formation of Balto-Slavic languages around 5.500 BC, which totally contradicts former theories according to which Slavic would have appeared much later and gives credit to the theories of renowned linguists as M. Meier-Brugger, K-H. Schmidt, N. Bird, E. Hamp or C. Beckwith underlining ancient links between Celtic and Eastern Indo-European languages, as Indo-Iranian and Slavic, already from the 5th millenary BC. I am thus astonished that this study places Celtic at the Western end of Europe, as it had an ancient presence in Danubic Europe and the Balkans.

The timeframe set in Bouckaert et al. (2012) also fits, besides the expansion of agriculture from Anatolia, with the development of megalithism, which expanded, according to Mosenkis' study *Dravidian Çatal Höyük, Ubaid, Balkan and West European Neolithic priest elite*, jointly with Dravidian religion and language, from Zagros (around 10.000 BC) to Çatal Höyük (7.400 BC-6.200 BC), Vinča (6.000-4.000 BC) and Gaul (around 5.000 BC). It also fits with genetic data from Dupanloup (2004) attesting that 30% of the French genetic pool, mainly Anatolian and Basque, came at the Neolithic, as for instance haplogroups Y-DNA H2, I M-170 and R1b, found from Iran, Anatolia and the Balkans to Gaul and characteristic of megalithic DNA. The presence of Dravidian haplogroups H2 and L-M20 in South Caucasus and Southern Europe confirms the Dravidian component of this Neolithic migration.

Khvorykh et al., (2020) promote the major role of Central Eurasia (Central Asia, Iran, Caucasus) in the transmission of genes. The peoples with the most diversified genes as Uighurs, Azeris, Uzbeks and Iranians carry roughly equal genetic contributions from the Middle East, Europe, China, and India. This study clearly shows that Neolithic migrations strongly modified the European genome by bringing Middle-Eastern, and in particular Anatolian genes (40%), in the same proportion as the genes of original hunter-gatherers (40%). Indian genes spread in decreasing proportion in Iran (20%), the Caucasus (14%) and Europe (5%). Arctic and Siberian genes mostly spread in North-Eastern Europe (15% against 5% elsewhere). Finally, African genes spread mostly in Southern Europe (10% in Spain and 7% in Italy). This study strengthens the theory of a major Neolithic migration from India and Central Asia to the Caucasus, Anatolia and Europe by the Balkans and Northern Africa.

Central Asia, at the crossroad of these influences, appears as a very serious candidate as original homeland of the ancestor of Indo-European, Dravidian and Ibero-Caucasian languages, of which Burushaski, which could have come from Altay, also bringing Altaic linguistic elements, as well as haplogroups R1a and R1b, which originated from Southern Siberia and spread to Europe, would be an archaic remnant, as Kalasha, archaic Indo-Aryan language of the Pamir. This spread is also corroborated by archaeological discoveries dating from the Gravettian in Altay, Pamir and Uzbekistan, according to researchers as Marcel Otte. This first migration brought haplogroup R1b in Italy (Villabruna, 14.000 BP), in France (12.000 BP) and in Serbia (11.000 BP) and was at the origin of the pyramids of Visoko in Bosnia and Herzegovina according to Rondu (2021). This is coherent with Arya (2019), dating the migration of Danaans to Europe around 13.000 BC. This early migration for the peopling of Europe from Anatolia and the Caucasus is also corroborated by Myres et al., (2011) study. Hallast (2015) genetic study confirms the Central Asian role on the formation of R1b stating that: "*The addition of Central Asian chromosomes here contributes a sequence to the deepest subclade of R1b M-269, whereas another, in a Bhutanese individual, forms an outgroup almost as old as the R1a/R1b split*". R1b M-269 and West-European subclades of this haplogroup, as R1b P-312, have been found in Central Asia according to genetic maps and studies, strengthening the theory of a Central Asian origin.

The alleged Pamirian origin of haplogroup L-M20, carried by 15% by the Burushos and 25% of the Kalash, found in the Caucasus, but also in Southern Europe, as well as the Pamirian origin of the Bulgarian genome, according to a study of S. Stoylov, and the proximity between the genome of Pamirian Tajiks

and Europeans according to E. Heyer also plead in this direction. St Clair's study of the distribution of haplogroup G2a, or G-M201, which appeared around 21.000 BC around Pamir according to A. Perdihi, also clearly shows genetic links between pastoralists and first farmers. According to St Clair's study, haplogroup G-M201 can be found at quite high frequencies by Kalash (20%), Burushos (5%), Dravidian Brahui (16%), Tajiks (11%), Hazaras (6%), Iranian Gilaki (16%), Assyrians (8%), Armenians (up to 42%), Kartvelians (up to 50%), Turks (6%), Greeks (9%), Bulgarians (5%), Italians (10%), Corsicans (22%), French (5%) and Western Iberians (6%).

The genetic and linguistic links between Brits, Basques, Czechs, Slovaks, Greeks, Armenians, Turks and Pamirian Yaghnobis and the crucial role of migrations from Central Asia are mentioned by Spencer-Wells et al. (2001).

The presence of features of Pamirian languages in Thracian, Bulgarian, Macedonian, Albanian and Aromanian, language of Vlachs, as *bac*, sheepfold in Burushaski, *bacija* in Balkan languages, and *zamiina*, earth in Burushaski, close to *zemlja*, earth, is also significant and could explain that the name of Zalmoxis, Thracian Grand Priest considered as being at the origin of Druidism, would have come from Dravidian. The presence even in modern French of words close to Burushaski linked to pastoralism and agriculture (**terre**, earth, close to *ter*, mountain pasture, **bélier**, ram, close to *belis*, ewe, lamb, **bouc**, he-goat, close to *buc*, he-goat, **charrue**, plow, close to *har*, plow, **pomme**, apple, close to *phamol*, fruit), family (**maman**, mother, close to *mama*, mother, **papa**, father, close to *bapo*, father, **fil**, **fille**, son, daughter, close to *pilili*, child), human body (**cœur**, heart, close to *guru*, heart, **bouche**, mouth, close to *buk*, throat), **feu**, fire, close to *phu*, fire, **servir**, serve, close to *ser*, serve, **je**, I, close to *je*, I, also close to *ja*, I in Slavic, **le**, the, close to *le*, the, and to articles from Balkan languages, as the presence in Gaulish, French and Slavic of many Dravidian and Burushaski words quoted in this study, also plead for a migration linked to the expansion of pastoralism and agriculture from Central Asia and the confines of India to the Caucasus, Anatolia, the Balkans and Western Europe at the Neolithic. This migration is attested by the arrival in France of goats carrying genes from Central Asia and Pakistan.

This migration brought to Europe an archaic Euro-Asiatic language, mixing features of the most archaic Indo-European languages of India and Anatolia, Dravidian, Elamite, Altaic and Ibero-Caucasian languages, which took part in the formation of Indo-European languages, of which Burushaski, classified by the famous linguist E. Hamp as the most archaic Indo-European language linked to Indo-Hittite, is a remnant. According to Horvath (2021), Burushaski was

the first language spoken on the Iranian plateau before being replaced by Elamo-Dravidian and later Indo-European, which tends to confirm the anteriority of Burushaski and the theory that this language, as Elamo-Dravidian, contributed to the formation of Indo-European languages. My theory is also coherent with Copeland's (2021) links of Indo-Europeans with Altaic and Uralic peoples, Akkadians and Hittites, which pleads for a migration of pastoralists by a Southern route from Altay to Ireland.

According to Kassian (2021) these languages stem from an original Eurasian language, which included Samoyedic languages from Siberia and split between 18.000 and 8.000 BC. My theory is also consistent with Pagel-Atkinson (2013) who postulates that the seven language families of Eurasia form a linguistic super-family which evolved from a common ancestor around 15,000 years ago, with a homeland in Central Asia, from which Dravidian, Kartvelian and Basque were the first to separate, followed by Proto-Indo-Europeans (PIE) around 8.700 years ago, which contradicts the theory of Kurgans, postulating a much later formation of PIE. Finally, my theory is consistent with Tarkhishvili (2014) who states that *"the Kartvelian and Dravidic language families hold the most basal position in a tree of Euro Asiatic languages (Bomhard and Kerns 1994; Pagel et al. 2013). Y-DNA haplogroups G and H dominant in speakers of these two linguistic groups: Kartvelian (this study; Yunusbayev et al. 2012) and Dravidic (Sengupta et al. 2006), respectively, similarly hold the most basal position in a tree of patrilineages descending from super haplogroup F widespread in Eurasia (Karafet et al. 2008). This fact may indicate correlated evolution of the G and H patrilineages and the Kartvelian and Dravidic languages, respectively"*. According to Sengupta et al., (2006) haplogroups F and H appeared in India around 30.000 years ago and haplogroup F gave birth to all Eurasian haplogroups, which supports my theory.

This latest theory is also supported by Mondal et al. (2017) stating that: *"Our time divergence estimate matches the previous studies which argued that most of the haplogroups present in India (C5, F*, H, L1 and R2) arose inside India rather than being brought from outside (Sengupta et al. 2006; Carvalho-Silva et al. 2006). The closest neighbours of Indian clades in our dataset are generally from Southern Europe (and not other European populations), a place known to have had more influence from the first Neolithic expansion from the Levant through Anatolia and less from the steppe migration which was perhaps responsible for the Indo-European expansion of languages in Europe (Haak et al. 2015). The time divergence between Indian and European Y-chromosomes, based on the closest neighbour analysis, shows two different distinctive divergence times for J2 and R1a, suggesting that the European ancestry in India is much older (>10 kya) than what would*

be expected from a recent migration of Indo-European populations into India (~4 to 5 kya). These results suggest that the European-related male ancestry in Indian populations might be much older and more complex than anticipated, and might originate from the first wave of agriculturists or even earlier, giving stronger support to the very old ages for Indian Y-chromosomes; it also downplays the importance of migration related to the Indo-Aryan linguistic expansion".

Another significant excerpt from the same study states that *"Surprisingly, the two South European populations (Toscans in Italia, TSI, and Iberian Population in Spain, IBS) are the closest neighbors of North Indian populations outside India (Fig. 4b); unfortunately in this data set there are no data available for West Asia to indicate a more plausible place where the two groups (India and South Europe) could have some partial common origin; future work in the regions will allow a more precise analysis. The distribution of time depths for the closest neighbors of Indians demonstrated two different clusters for these two South European populations (Fig. 4c). One is common to all Europeans and close to 38.6 kya (± 7.4 kya), while the second is more specific to South Europeans (TSI and IBS) and around 13.9 kya (± 4.6 kya). However, we need to stress that the absence of a relevant sample (likely from Western Asia) in the closest neighbor analysis can lead to a higher time of divergence than the true divergence"*.

Finally, it is worth citing the interesting study by Raghavan et al., (2013) which underlines the genetic links between Indians and Tajiks, French, Sardinians, but also Caucasian Avars, who may have come from Mongolia, and Finno-Uralic Maris of the Volga, all linked to the Malta boy which brought haplogroup R 24.000 years ago, which gives credit to a common origin and an original trans-Eurasian language.

6. CONCLUSION

All these recent studies lead me to conclude, on the basis of this interdisciplinary study based on linguistic, genetic, historical, archaeological, agricultural and religious studies, that Indo-European languages stemmed from a Trans-Eurasian original language which originated in Central Asia and expanded from there with agriculture and pastoralism. I am aware that my present critical review study won't close the never-ending controversy about the original homeland of Indo-Europeans but I hope however it will bring a useful contribution to the debate.

As a final word, I will quote the study of the Chinese researcher Rongxing Guo (2021) according to whom all ancient civilisations, Chinese, Indian, Mesopotamian, Egyptian, European and even American would stem from an ancestral civilisation in which wadi and various variants as wan, meaning between others river, valley, forest, mountain, mother-earth,

can be found with a religious connotation in numerous languages - as Dravidian and Gaulish. Moreover, the root wa can also be found in names of Gods as Dewa, Siwa or Yahweh as in akwa, water, which can be found in many languages. About 50 words as tata, dad, mama, mum, mako, child, viro, man, bena, women, meno, think, gabi, take, da, give, беру, carry, cleu, hear, kahla, speak, edo, eat, itao, go, aro, plough, gabala, head, aedu, fire, bergo, hill, corro, summit, temos, dark, kolo, wheel, bitu, life, maros, big, which can be found in many languages as Gaulish and Dravidian, could come from this original language.

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APPENDIX 1

Verbs:

Love/aimer: **lubi**, I love **lubiu**, linked to ljubiti in c. sl., ljubiti in BSCM, lubjo in PIE and lubh in Sanskrit

Ask/demander: **petā**, I ask **petami**, linked to pitat in c. sl., pitati in BSCM, pet in Etruscan

Give/donner: **da**, I give **dami**, from dat, dati (c. sl., BSCM), da (Sanskrit, Hittite), ntan (Bur), tar (Drav), ta (TE)

Give out/distribuer: **danos**, same roots, from da (PIE, Sanskrit), tar (Drav), ntan (Bur), duna (Elam), ta (TE)

Know, guide/savoir, guider: **vedo**, I know **vedu**, linked to vedet, know, voditi, guide (BSCM), vidjeti, see (BSCM), weid, know, see, wed, guide in PIE, veda, vid in Sanskrit, veda, guide, vida, see in Glozelian

Lie/coucher: **leg**, I lie **legu**, linked to ležat (c. sl.), ležati (BSCM), leg (PIE), lag (Kartv, Hittite), malagu (Drav)

Want/vouloir: **vel**, I want **velu**, linked to velet (Czech), velti (Lithuanian), weltis (PIE), want, venti, want, aval, vel, desire (Drav), awaaji, need (Bur.), linked to **avillos**, desirable (Gaulish), želit, desire (c. sl.), željeti (BSCM)

Adore/adorer: **voleo**, I adore **volu**, linked to voljeti, love in BSCM, vilay, desire, love in Dravidian

Think/penser: **meno**, linked to minit, think (Czech), man, think (Drav), men, think (PIE), manu, think (TE)

Buy/acheter: **prina**, I buy **prinami**, linked to Russian krenut, buy, from PIE krin and Sanskrit krināti

Hear/entendre: **cleu**, I hear **cluiu**, from clas, ear (old Sl., BSCM), PIE kleu, Drav kel, Bur dokoyal, TE kul, hear

Hold/tenir: I hold, **delgu**, linked to dalaga (Glozel), deržu, I hold (Russian), držati (BSCM), derg (PIE), hear

Beat/frapper: **bi**, I beat **biu**, linked to c. sl. bit, beat, biti in BSCM, pattu in Dravidian

Say/dire: **spatus**, **sagio**, linked to skazat, say (Russian), kazati (BSCM), p replacing k, esa (Drav), etas (Bur.)

Know/connaitre: **gn**, I know **gnoiu**, known, **gnatos**, linked to znat, znaiu, (Russian), znati (BSCM), gnosketi (PIE), know, poznati (BSCM), gnotos, known, janati in Sanskrit, kan in Drav, henas in Bur, kena, know (TE)

Live/vivre: **biu**, linked to žit (c. sl.), živjeti (BSCM), jivati (Sanskrit), biyu (Altaic), pu (Drav.), ba, ji (Bur)

See/voir: **vid**, linked to vida (Glozel), videt (c. sl.), vidja (Bulgarian), vidjeti (BSCM), vid (Thracian, Sanskrit)

Carry/porter: **ber**, I carry, **beru**, linked to brat, beru in Russian, take, brati (BSCM), bhero (PIE), poru, beru (Drav), baart, bring (Bur), para (Hittite), bara (Avestan), bheru (TE); **beru** has many meanings, I take, I carry, I take with me, I bring back, I judge, I interpret a dream, I gain, I obtain, I spend time, I last, I endure, I give

Express an opinion/porter une opinion: **berna**, also linked to **beru** (Gaulish, Drav), bhero (PIE), barne (Bur)

Take a judgment/porter un jugement: **barnami**, **barn**, judge, **britu**, judgment, from **beru**, bhero, barne (Bur)

Speak/parler: **labarao**, **garo**, linked to govorit, speak (c. sl.), laprdati (Bosnian slang), laparaki, gar (Georgian), lapana (Sanskrit) lapana, speak, galaba, discuss, paray, kuru, speak, beron, language (Drav), laau, baret, gar (Burushaski); **radio**, rada (Glozel), linked to BSCM reci, Drav paray; **iac**, linked to c. sl. jazik, tongue, Bur yek

Discuss/discuter: **galo**, linked to golos, voice (c. sl.), galgaljo (PIE), galaba (Drav), gar (Bur), kahla, speak (TE)
 Call/appeler: **galo**, linked to glasati se in BSCM, kal, kare in Drav, gar in Bur, kahla, speak in TE
 Be/être: **bi**, **beto**, I am, **esmi** (jesam in BSCM), be, **biete**, linked to bit in c. sl., biti in Bosnian, bhu in Sanskrit, ba in Bur, pu, puttu in Dravidian (come to existence, be born), biyu in Altaic, buion, existence in Glozelian
 Complain/se lamenter: **ceio**, linked to kajati se, complain in Bulgarian, regret in BSCM, from Avestan kay
 Glorify/glorifier: **clebos**, linked to slaviti, glorify in c. sl., slaviti in BSCM, from PIE klewos, glory
 Breathe/respirer: **adiat**, linked to dah, breathe in Bulgarian, disati, breathe in BSCM, duh in PIE
 Protect/protéger: **cavo**, linked to čuvat, protect (Old Bulgarian), čuvati, protect (BSCM), ka, protect (Drav)
 Take/prend: **gabi**, from gepi, take (Bulgarian), zgrabi (BSCM), gabis (Vinča), ghe, steel (Burushaski), kavar (Dravidian), kaba (Altaic), kab (Kartvelian) may stem from kaba, take in the original Trans-Eurasian language
 Shout/crier: **iegumi**, linked to old Slavic jekati, may come from yako, shout in Evenk (Altaic), yek, name (Bur)
 Drink/boire: I drink, **ibu**, linked to piju (Russian), pijem (BSCM), I drink, pik (Kalash), pibia, be drunk (Drav)
 Go/aller: I go, **agu**, **itao**, linked to idti, idu (Russian), ici, idem (BSCM), iti (Sanskrit), itt (Hittite), agu, aydu, go (Drav), hatya, I go (Kalash), hata, go, walk (Bur), hajde (BSCM); the derived word **adagu**, linked to odeidu, odem, uditi (Sanskrit), odu, udugu (Drav) has many meanings: I go, I drive, I push, I place, I set in movement, I impose, I inflict, I give, I raise, I bring, I set forth, I take a woman, I begin, I undertake, I proceed to
 Drive/conduire: **itaro**, also linked to **itao** and the same Slavic and PIE roots, to Bur hata and Drav idaru, travel
 Go/aller: **poudo**, linked to BSCM putovati, travel, poći, go, PIE pent, road and Dravidian pogu, go
 Go/aller: **steigo**, linked to Bulgarian stigat, come, stići in BSCM and steigho in PIE
 Come/venir: **davo**, linked to the same roots, dođti in Russian, doći in BSCM and va, come in Dravidian
 Drive/conduire: **covegno**, **suvendo**, linked to c. sl. vodit, BSCM voditi, and Drav kum, with and vandi, go
 Walk/marcher: **voreto**, linked to varvja, walk (Bulgarian), walesac sie, wander (Polish), valay, walk (Drav)
 Run/courir: **restu**, linked to riskati in Old Bulgarian, hrjasti in Ukrainian, may come from old Slavic gresti
 Run out/filer: **teko**, linked to utekat, run out in common Slavic, otuka, odu in Dravidian, run, go aside
 Scream/gémir: **stano**, linked to stana, scream in Bulgarian, stenjati in BSCM
 Mix/mélanger: **mesga**, linked to mesja (Bulgarian), miješati (BSCM), mešati (Slovenian), PIE miksejo, mix
 Walk/marcher: **ke**, linked to šetati in BSCM, have a walk, šetam in Bulgarian, hata in Burushaski
 Accuse/accuser: **comsoudo**, linked to c. sl. sudit, judge, suditi in BSCM
 Sit down/s'asseoir: **sedo**, linked to c. sl. sedet, sjesti in BSCM, sit down, sidati in Sanskrit, sit down, sit in Bur Cut/couper: **seco**, linked to c. sl. sekati, PIE sek, BSCM sjeći, Vinča speech sek, cut, sekuris, axe (PIE), sagaris, axe (Scythian), sekira, axe (c. sl., BSCM), sagari, sickle (Dravidian), skarc, cut (Burushaski) sahsi, cut (Elamite)
 Defame/diffamer: **cablaro**, linked to klebeta in Bulgarian and klevetati in BSCM, defame
 Buy/acquérir: **cabo**, linked to kupit, buy in common Slavic, kupiti in BSCM, kon in Dravidian
 Feast/festoyer: **comedo**, linked to edo, jest (c. sl.), jesti (BSCM), edmi (PIE), ite (Alt), eat, kum and jad (Drav)
 Eat/manger: **edo**, linked to jest, jesti (c. sl., BSCM), edmi (PIE), ad (Sanskrit), jad (Drav), ite (Alt.), ed (Hittite), ita (TE), eat
 Stick/adhérer: **glina**, linked to glina, clay in sl. c., **gloido** in Gaulish, klej, glue in sl. c., from PIE glej, Drav kol
 Desire/désirer: **lato**, linked to laska, love in Czech, laskati, compliment in BSCM, could come from Altaic
 Lick/lécher: **leigo**, linked to lizat, lick in Slavic, lizati in BSCM, last, lick in Burushaski, laka, lick in TE
 Rest, calm/se reposer, se calmer: **samo**, linked to smiriti se (BSCM), **sam**, quiet, linked to samis in PIE
 Jump/sauter: **skak**, linked to skakat, jump in Slavic, skakati in BSCM, from PIE skek, Dravidian kuti, jump
 Scrub/gratter: **skrib**, linked to skrobat in Slavic, škrabati in Bosnian, scrub
 Shout/crier: **skrizda**, linked to kričat, shout in Slavic, kričati in BSCM, from krošati in Sanskrit
 Slip/glisser: **sleid**, linked to slizgat, slip in Slavic, sklizati in BSCM, could come from Dravidian lamba
 Stand/se dresser, se maintenir: **stao**, linked to stat (c. sl.), stajati (BSCM), sta (Sanskrit), dstay (Bur), istanday (Hittite), statiivi (Uralic)
 Lay/poser: **sista**, from **sta**, stand, linked to stat (c. sl.), stajati (BSCM), sta (Sanskrit), dstay (Bur), istanday (Hittite), statiivi (Uralic)
 Melt/fondre: **taio**, linked to taiat in c. sl., taljiti in BSCM, titami in PIE, tajin in Ossetian, melt, tao, flow in Bur
 Flow/couler: **liyo**, linked to lit, pour in Czech, liat, pour in Slovak, lijevati, pour in BSCM, laya in TE
 Search/chercher: **sagi**, linked to iskat, search in Russian and segh, search in PIE
 Suffer/pâtir, souffrir: **passa**, patha (Glozel) linked to patit (c.sl.), patiti (BSCM), suffer, patu (Dravidian), suffer
 Carry/porter: **troga**, linked to traga, pull (Glozel), tragat (c. sl., Romanian), drag, tocana (Dravidian), carry
 Spare/épargner: **smerto**, linked to sberegat in Russian, spare

NB: according to the French/Gaulish dictionary, the first person of singular ends in u, iu or mi for verbs ending in a. Hence the proposed endings, without certainty, similar to Slavic

Words linked to family:

Dad, father/papa, père: **tatis**, tata (Glozel), linked to tata (c. sl.), **ater**, linked to ata (Slovenian), otac (BSCM), tata and attas (PIE), tata, attam (Dravidian), atta (Elamite), tati, atta, (Hittite), tata (Burushaski)
 Mother, mum/mère, maman: **matir**, **mama**, linked to mat, mama (c. sl.), mater, mati in BSCM, mama (Bur) amman, attei (Drav), amma (Elam), Mamma, Matrikas, Mother Goddess (Drav), would have given matrone
 Man/homme: **viro**, linked to wiros, man (PIE), oior, man (Scythian), vir (Hittite), ferta, man (Bulgarian), vyras, man (Lithuanian), vir, man (Vinča), vir, brave man (Drav), wer, man (Kartvelian), biru (Bur), viril (French)
 Women/femme: **dea**, linked to da, mother (Scythian, Georgian), djeva (BSCM), virgin, taj, mother (Dravidian)
 Women/femme: **vena**, linked to žena, wife (sl. c.), b replacing g in Gaulish, gwen (PIE), genis (Bur), pen (Drav, TE); Bona means woman in Bosnian and bonne maid in French, which also has the pejorative bonne femme
 Young woman/jeune fille: **geneta**, linked to Yo, Goddess of Fertility (Glozel), Yoni, Mother-Goddess (Dravidian culture of Indus), žena, woman (c. sl., BSCM), jani, woman (Sanskrit), cinnadi, young woman (Drav), genis (Bur), guen (Hittite), kuni (TE); **morugena**, linked to žena, woman (c. sl., BSCM), from mari, young, and zana, woman in Elamite
 Daughter/fille: **duxtir**, linked to doč (Russian), dašterja, (Bulgarian), dasin (Bur), dughter (PIE), ir (Drav)

Son/fils, garçon: **mapos, magos**, maqa (Glozel), linked to momak (Bosnian), p replacing k in Gaulish, PIE maqos, Dravidian maka, mago, Altaic muko; **muskatos**, young man, linked to muškarac in BSCM
 Brother/frère: **brater**, linked to brat in c. sl. and BSCM, bhrater in PIE, bhratr in Sanskrit, pracar in Tocharian
 Sister/sœur: **suesor, suestos**, linked to sestra, sister (c. sl., BSCM), swesor (PIE), svasr (Sanskrit), sutu (Elam)
 Nephew/neveu: **neptos**, linked to nećak, nephew in BSCM, nepot, nephew (PIE), anip, relative (Elamite), nekna, brother (Hittite)
 Niece/niece: **nepta**, linked to nećakinja, niece in BSCM, from nepot, nephew (PIE), anip, relative (Elamite)
 Stepmother-father/belle-mère, beau-père: **svekru, svekrno**, linked to svekrva, svekar (BSCM), skir (Bur), PIE
 Widow/veuve: **widwa**, linked to vdova in c sl., udovica in BSCM, vidhava in Sanskrit
 Descendant: **selos**, linked to čeljad, descendant in Bulgarian and BSCM, and to Altaic kelu-me
 Family/famille: **catus**, linked to kentas, child in Thracian, čado, child in old Slavic, BSCM, čanda, child in Drav

Words linked to animals:

Lamb/agneau: **ognos**, oagna in Glozelian, linked to jagnjata, lamb in Slavic, jagnje in BSCM, jagnja in Sanskrit
 Ewe/brebis: **ovica**, linked to ovca (c. sl., BSCM), owis (PIE), avi (Sanskrit), huis (Bur), hawi (Hittite), eve (Akkadian)
 Shepherd/berger: **ovitarios**, also linked to ovca, ovčar, shepherd in BSCM and Slovenian, avipala in Sanskrit
 Cat/chat, chatte: **cattos, catta**, linked to kot in Polish, katta in PIE, kotti in Dravidian, cat
 Goose/oie: **gansis**, linked to ges, gus, guska, goose in Polish, Russian and BSCM, gans in PIE, gaso in Altaic
 Crow/corbeau: **branos**, linked to the Slavic word vrana, crow, also in BSCM, from the PIE worn
 Crow/corbeau: **garanos**, linked to BSCM gavran, Bulgarian garvan, Drav karaku, Bur garuuyo, TE kara, crane
 Crow/corbeau: **krouk**, linked to kruk, crow in Polish, and to the Dravidian karaku, Burushaski garuuyo
 Crane/grue: **garanos**, linked to žuraw, crane in Polish, PIE gerh, garuuyo, heron in Bur, Dravidian karaku
 Cow/vache: **keva**, linked to gu, cow, guta, Goddess-Cow (Glozel), govoda (Slovenian), gava (Sanskrit, Avestan), cevū, bull (Drav), kovi, cow (Tocharian), korova (Russian), krava (BSCM), karuvu (Drav), cow, linked to **karnon**, horn, Drav kor, Bur kar, TE kera, horn, har, ox, qarnu, horn (Akkadian), kraun, horn (Hittite)
 Hedgehog/hérisson: **egi**, linked to jež, hedgehog in Slavic and BSCM, from the PIE eghi
 Owl/chouette: **cava**, linked to sova (Bulgarian, Slovenian, BSCM, c replacing s in Gaulish, ga in Altaic
 Beaver/castor: **beber**, linked to bober in Slovenian, bobar in Bulgarian, dabar in BSCM and bhebhros in PIE
 Horse/cheval: **caballos**, linked to kobila, mare (c. sl., BSCM), to Drav seval, stallion, PIE kablnos, Bur kabut Horse/cheval: **marca**, linked to marca in Thracian, mrha in Slovenian, mrkov in Serbian, markos in PIE, morv in Altaic, mari, young horse, mare in Dravidian
 Horse/cheval: komonj, battle horse in Slave, from which came konj, horse in c. sl., is linked to **cammanios**, horse riding in Gaulish, konk, horse in Celtic, kanam, food for horses in Dravidian
 Bull/taureau: **tarvos**, linked to tura (Bulgarian), tur (Czech), taru (Vinča), bull, toru, ox (Drav), tor (Burushaski)
 Pig/porc: **su, sua**, su in Glozelian, linked to svinja, pig in c. sl. and BSCM, sus, swinos in PIE, su in Sanskrit
 Pig/porc: **orko**, linked to prasa in common Slavic, prase in BSCM, pig, from porko in PIE with loss of the p
 Deer/cerf: **elantia**, linked to jelen in common Slavic and BSCM, from elen in PIE, ilaru in Drav, elgit in Bur
 Goat/chèvre: **iorcos**, linked to jarak (Serbian), jarac, he-goat (Bosnian), jorkos (PIE), elgit (Bur) era, goat (Drav) Hen/poule: **kerka**, linked to c. sl. kura, hen, kokoška in BSCM, from kerkos, hen in PIE, kor, hen in Dravidian, koška being the plural of kor in Dravidian, which consolidates this etymology
 Chicken/poulet: **cerca**, linked to kurica (c. sl.), kokoš in BSCM, from kerkos, hen in PIE, kor, cock in Dravidian
 Wolf/loup: **volpos**, linked to volk in Slavic, vuk in BSCM, p replacing k in Gaulish, from viqo, vlqo in PIE
 Weasel/belette: **assa**, linked to the Czech jasienska and BSCM lasica, weasel
 Chamois: **kamoke**, linked to kamzik in Czech, could come from Drav gana, sheep flock, Elam kumas, he-goat
 Carp/carpe: **karpa**, linked to karp or kapr in Slavic, carp, korbu in Kartv, can come from the original language
 Salmon, sturgeon/saumon, esturgeon: **asso-esox**, losos, salmon (c. sl.), jesetr (BSCM, c. sl.), azin (Alt), sturgeon
 Ant/fourmi: **morvi**, linked to mravenec, ant in Czech, mrav in BSCM, morwi in PIE
 Snail/escargot: **selekio**, linked to slimak, snail in Polish, from sleimaks in PIE
 Bear/ours: **matu**, linked to medved in c. sl., from Sanskrit madhvad, honey eater, matu, honey in Dravidian
 Squirrel/écureuil: **viveros**, linked to wiewiorka, squirrel in Polish, vjeverica, squirrel in BSCM
 Nest/nid: **nizdo**, linked to gniezdo in c. sl., gnijezdo in BSCM, nest, from PIE nisdos, Armenian nist, nest
 Animal leg/patte: **uranka**, linked to ruka, arm (Russian, BSCM), from Dravidian eraka, arm, Bur ren, hand
 Small/petit animal: **milo**, linked to mali, small in c. sl., milo, small and dear (BSCM), mari, young in Dravidian

Words linked to agriculture:

Seat, saddle/siège, selle: **sedlon, sedo**, linked to sedlo, saddle in Slavic and BSCM, sedla, seat in PIE
 Oat/avoine: **ieva**, linked to evja, grain (old Slavic), java (Sanskrit) juwari (Kalash), viya (Drav), bay (Bur)
 Rye/seigle: **sata**, linked to žito, rye in c. sl. and BSCM, sitya in Sanskrit, sita, kind of wheat in Glozelian
 Hoe/houe: **kapia**, linked to kopač, hoe in Bulgarian, and to kopati in BSCM
 Flax, linen/lin: **lino**, linked to the old Slavic linu, Russian len and BSCM lan, from the PIE lino
 Pieu: **stabo**, linked to stobor in Bulgarian and stablo, trunk in BSCM
 Plough/labourer: **aratro, arare**, linked to orat, plough (c. sl.), orati (BSCM), ar (Drav), har, (Bur), harpi (Elam), hars (Hittite), harasu (Akkadian), aruthi (Hurro-Urartian), are (Tocharian)
 Agriculture, cultivate, plough/agriculture, cultivar, labourer: **aro**, same roots, from PIE aratron, arjo, Drav ar
 Farmer/agriculteur: **artaios**, same roots, can be linked to the old Slavic ortaj, Bur har and Dravidian uravan
 Plough, swing plough/charrue, araire: **ario**, same roots, linked to Scythian arei, ploughman, Drav ar, Bur. har
 Plough/charrue: **aratro**, linked to oralo, plough (Bulgarian), orat, orati, plough (sl.c.), (k)ar(u) (Drav), har (Bur)
 Joke/joug: **jugo**, linked to igo (BSCM), jeugom (Vinča), yuga (Sanskrit), nukam (Drav), iukan (Hittite)
 Grain: **carnu**, linked to zrno (BSCM, Czech), karn, grind in Dravidian, gur, wheat, gur malao, millet in Bur
 Seed/graine: **asiam**, semo (Glozel), linked to sjeme, seed (BSCM), semn (PIE), simbi (Dravidian), siman (Elam)
 Grain: **granio**, linked to gran (Czech), granio (PIE), hrana, food (BSCM), gur, wheat (Bur), karn, grind (Drav)

Billhook/serpe: **serro**, linked to serp or srp (sl. c., BSCM), srpa (PIE), sagari, sickle (Drav), bisars, sickle (Bur)
 Spade/pelle: **palo**, linked to bel, spade in Bulgarian, and lopata, spade in BSCM and Russian
 Miller/meunier: **melitorios**, linked to c. sl. melit, grind, mljeti in BSCM, melo in PIE, mel, grind in Dravidian
 Grind/moudre: **melo**, from PIE melo, Altaic mole, mel, grind (Drav), mul, gruel (Bur), malla, grind (Hittite), mola, grind (TE)
 Milk a cow/traire une vache: **mlitsi**, linked to mleko, milk in Slavic, mljeko in BSCM

Words linked to food and beverages:

Food, life/nourriture, vie: **biveto**, linked to biće, existence (BSCM), pitu (Sanskrit), phiti (Bur), putu (Drav)
 Food/nourriture: **mastia**, linked to meso, meat or mast, smear (BSCM), mas (Sanskrit), mos (Kalash), meat
 Water/eau: **od**, **boglo**, linked to voda (c. sl.), wodr, woda (PIE), water, otam (Dravidian), budoo (Burushaski), uda (Sanskrit), watar (Hittite), water, could come from weta, oda, water in the original Transeurasian language
 Wine/vin: **vinom**, linked to vino, wine in c. sl. and BSCM, woinom in PIE, wina in Hittite, ghvino in Georgian
 Cook/cuisinier: **poppos**, **pep**, linked to pekar, baker (BSCM), peqo (PIE, Altaic), bege, fire, becc, cook, puka, food (Drav), pać (Sanskrit), paqu, loaf of bread (Bur), pec, hot in Kalash, which gave peći, cook, in Slovenian, from peku, hot, pica, cook (TE)
 Cook/cuisinière: **popa**, linked to the same roots; moreover, klopa means food in Bosnian
 Baker/boulangier: **poperos**, linked to the same roots, pekar, baker in BSCM, paqu, loaf of bread in Burushaski
 Kitchen/cuisine: **popano**, linked to the same roots, from the PIE peqtis, kitchen
 Salt/sel: **salo**, linked to the Slavic and BSCM sol, **salto**, salted, slan in BSCM, from sal in PIE
 Honey/miel: **melu**, linked to med, honey (c. sl., BSCM), melit (PIE, Hittite), madhu (Sanskrit), mattu (Drav), also linked to mel, resin in Elamite, mel, mild in Dravidian, also found in the Caucasian mal, from majla (TE)
 Mead/hydromel: **medu**, linked to med, honey (c. sl., BSCM), madhu (Sanskrit), mattu (Drav), mel, wine (Bur)
 Onion, garlic/oignon, ail: **cremo**, **kasnina**, linked to Bulgarian kromid, kremusom (PIE), česnok, garlic in c. sl.
 Milk/lait: **melgos**, linked to mljeko (BSCM), moloko (Russian), molgije (PIE), mal (Drav), malke (Tokharian) Smear/graisse: **smer**, **smero**, smear, linked to Polish smar, smear, from the PIE smerus
 Apple/pomme: **aballo**, linked to jabalka (Bulgarian), jabolko (Slovenian), jabuka (BSCM), abolo (Vinča), abelos (PIE), balt (Burushaski)
 Bilberry/myrtille: **brucos**, linked to boruvka in Czech, borowka in Polish, borovnica in BSCM
 Carrot/carotte: **mekon**, linked to Russian markov, carrot, mrkva in BSCM, mrka in PIE
 Soup/soupe: **iutta**, **jusko**, linked to juha, soup in Croatian, from the PIE jus, Dravidian jupa, liquid food
 Flour/farine: **mlato**, from mole (alt.), melit (c. sl.), grind, mljeti (BSCM), mel (Drav), mul (Bur), malla (Hittite)
 Dough/pâte: **tausto**, linked to testo, dough in common Slavic, tijesto in BSCM
 Juice/jus: **sugo**, linked to sok, juice in Slavic and BSCM, soukos in PIE, maybe Drav saru, Bur cel, juice
 Spoon/cuiller: **leiga**, linked to ližica, cuiller in Slavic, žlica in Croatian, from leigla in PIE
 Inn/auberge: **kurmi-tegos**, house where you drink beer (kremon in PIE), linked to krčma in Slavic and BSCM

Words linked to trees:

Oak, wood/chêne, bois: **dervo**, from drvo (BSCM), daru (Thracian), druea (Vinča), dru (Sanskrit), taru (Hittite)
 Beech/hêtre: **bagos**, linked to buk, beech in Slavic, bukva in BSCM, from bego in PIE, behek in Burushaski
 Elm/orme: **lemo**, linked to the Russian ilem, elm
 Yew/if: **ivos**, **eburos**, linked to iva, willow in Russian and BSCM, and bor in Bulgarian, BSCM and Slovenian
 Maple/érable: **abolos**, linked to javor in BSCM and Czech and jablan in Bosnian, poplar
 Service tree/cormier: **kormia**, from korm (c. sl.), krmi (BSCM), kur (Drav), garma (Bur), food, **kurmi**, beer
 Lime/tilleul: **leima**, linked to lipa, lime in common Slavic and BSCM, from leipa in PIE
 Alder/aulne, verne: **verna**, linked to vrba in BSCM and Czech, willow, from PIE wernas
 Pine/pin: **osno**, linked to sosna, pine in Russian, Polish, Czech
 Forest/foret: **gorca**, linked to gorica, small forest in Bulgarian, gora, wooded mountain in BSCM
 Apple orchard/pommerai: **abalon**, linked to iablon, apple tree in Russian, jabuka in BSCM
 Beech forest/hêtraie: **bokonia**, linked to buk, beech, bukva in BSCM, bego in PIE, behek in Burushaski
 Wooded countryside/bocage: **leno**, linked to the common Slavic les, forest
 Orchard/verger: **baciua**, linked to bašta, bača, garden (BSCM), bagh, garden (Sanskrit, Persian), basi in Bur
 Branch/branche: **canka**, linked to sanka, branch (Old Bulgarian), kankus (Vinča), konka (Drav), sak, arm (Bur)
 Forest/foret: **ceto**, **ketiya**, linked to četa (Bulgarian, Slovenian), četinarja, resinous forest (BSCM), katu (Drav)
 Shrub/arbuste: **prestio**, linked to krzak, shrub (Polish), hrast, oak (BSCM), from the PIE krsnos, shrub

Words linked to nature:

Swamp/marécage: **bagno**, linked to Polish bagno, **mucuno**, linked to BSCM močvara and Bulgarian mokrište, **lato**, linked to blato (Bulgarian, Slovenian, BSCM), from lat (PIE), bel (Bur), ula, mud (Drav), lata, wet (TE)
 Land plot/parcelle de terre: **olca**, linked to polosa (c. sl.), plaša (BSCM), with loss of p, pallam, landplot (Drav)
 Sea/mer: **mori**, linked to morje in c. sl. and BSCM, mar in Thracian, mori in Scythian, mari in PIE and Drav
 Clay/glaise: **glesa**, **glisia**, linked to glina, clay in Slavic and BSCM, could be linked to kol, stick in Dravidian
 River/fleuve: **danu**, linked to Danube, Danu (Vinča), Don, Dnieper, Dniester, Rhône (Rhodanus), Odon in Brittany, Scythian, PIE danus, Drav tundna, pour water, Bur dala, channel, Kartv dun, flow, Elam da
 River/fleuve: **renos**, linked to Rhine, **iko**, linked to rijeka, river in c. sl. and BSCM, with loss of r, from rei, flow in PIE, ru, orivu, river in Drav, oruku, flow in Drav, ar, river in Hurrian, eku, water (TE)
 River/rivière: **onna**, which gave Yonne, Saone, Una, Sana, Bosna, from Drav amm, Elam hun, TE jama, water
 River/rivière: **proudis**, linked to prud, stream in common Slavic, oruku, flow in Dravidian
 Spring/source: **beru**, linked to izvor in BSCM and Bulgarian, from bheru, spring in PIE, uru, spring in Drav
 Lake/lac: **louco**, linked to lokev in Slovenian, loky, pond, lakus, lake in PIE, lanka, valley in Ossetian
 Bridge/pont: **briva**, linked to brv, bridge in Slovenian, brivna in Bulgarian, brvno in BSCM, bhrewa in PIE
 Moor/lande: **landa**, linked to Russian liada and BSCM landa, wilderness, londhom, land in PIE
 Plain/plaine: **lano**, linked to poljana, plain, polje, field (sl. c., BSCM), plano, flat in PIE, pallam in Dravidian
 Land/terre: **ialo**, linked to ila, mud (Bulgarian), ilovača, compost, jalov, barren land (BSCM), ula (Dravidian)

Hill, mount/colline, mont: **briga**, **bergo**, **barro**, linked to brdo, brijeg, hill (BSCM, Slovenian, Bulgarian), berg (Thracian), breg (Georgian), bhroigos, summit (PIE), berkat, hill (Bur), porrai, fortified hill (Drav), perunu, fortified hill (Hittite), pur, fortified town (Sanskrit), boru, stronghold (Old Bulgarian, Pamirian, Persian), from berg, high (TE)
 Dune, hill/colline, tumulus: **duno**, **dumyon**, linked to dun (Thracian), djuna (Bulgarian), dina (BSCM), don (Bur), dimmi (Drav), dunnu, fortified place (Akkadian) from which came dimb, kurgan in PIE and Romanian; kurgan also comes from Dravidian
 Hill/colline: **mello**, linked to mola, hill in Old Bulgarian, and malaï, hill in Drav, from mala, mountain (TE)
 Hill/colline: **cambos**, linked to kapa in Thracian, kopa in Slovenian, koppa, kumba, hill in Dravidian
 Rock/rocher: **acanno**, linked to kamen, stone (c. sl., BSCM), acmon (Thracian, PIE), asmanaca (Avestan)
 Flagstone/dalle: **lica**, could be linked to plita, plaque in c. sl., lana, plateau in Glozelian, planina, mountain in BSCM, which would come from rocky terrace, the p falling in Gaulish, and to litica, cliff in BSCM
 Summit/sommet: **corro**, linked to krai (Bulgarian), okris (PIE), summit, kar, rocky (Dravidian), goro, stone (Burushaski), gurunnu, summit (Akkadian), gora, mountain (Slavic, Georgian), gora, high (Basque), kara (TE)
 Sky/ciel: **nemos**, linked to nebo, sky (c. sl., BSCM), nabha (Sanskrit), vanam (Dravidian with loss of va)
 Cloud/nuage: **nebls**, also linked to nebo, sky, PIE nhebes, cloud, nebis, sky (Hittite) and vanam in Dravidian
 Wind/vent: **ventos**, linked to veter in c. sl. and BSCM, vata in Sanskrit, vata, vandu, wind in Dravidian
 Wet weather/temps humide: **wolko**, linked to vlhko, wet in Czech and Slovak, vlažan, wet in BSCM
 Sun/soleil: **sonno**, **sauli**, linked to sonce (c. sl.), sunce (BSCM), saul (Scythian), sul, burn (Drav), sa, sun (Bur)
 Sunset/coucher de soleil, occident: **sauli-sedata**, linked to sauli, sun and sedet, sit down in common Slavic
 Moon/lune: **louna**, linked to Russian luna, moon, louksna, moon in PIE, ilanka, shine in Dravidian

Words linked to body and health:

Head/tête: **gabala**, from golova, glava, (Russian, BSCM), ghebhla (PIE), gapal (Bur), bhala, forehead (Drav), kapa, head (TE)
 Arm/bras: **brek** in Celtic, linked to ruka, arm in common Slavic and BSCM, from eraka, arm (Drav), ren (Bur)
 Knee/genou: **glin**, linked to koleno in common Slavic, koljeno in BSCM, from kel in PIE, kanu in Dravidian
 Hair/cheveu: **voltos**, linked to volos, hair in Russian, vlasi in BSCM, from wolnos in PIE, val in Dravidian
 Belly/ventre: **bru** in Celtic, linked to brukho, belly in Russian, bricho in Czech, from bura in Dravidian
 Ear/oreille: **aus**, linked to usho, ear in Bulgarian, uho, ear in BSCM, from ousis in PIE
 Eye/Œil: **ops**, **oklo**, linked to oko, eye (c. sl.), oqos (Vinča), aks, sight, kon (Drav), elči (Bur), huka (TE), eye
 Sight/vue: **okulos**, also linked to oko, eye in Slavic, aks, sight in Dravidian, elči, eye in Bur, oči, eyes in Shina
 Nose/nez: **nasios**, linked to c. sl. nos, nose, Sanskrit nas, nose, and probably Dravidian muso, Bur mos, nose
 Eyebrow/sourcils: **bruvi**, linked to brovi (Russian), obrve (BSCM), bhrus (PIE), buru (Drav), bur (Burushaski)
 Mouth, lips/bouche, lèvres: **bussu**, linked to pusa, mouth (Czech), kiss (BSCM), bukka (Drav), buk (Bur)
 Mouth/bouche: **stam**, oza (Glozel), linked to usta, mouth (Bulgarian, BSCM, Slovenian), os (PIE), utatu (Drav)
 Barb/barbe: **granda**, linked to broda, barb in Slavic, brada in BSCM, from the PIE bharda
 Cheeks/joue: **likko**, linked to lico, face in common Slavic, lice in BSCM
 Neck/cou: **varro**, linked to vrat, neck in Bulgarian, BSCM and Slovenian
 Ass/fesse: **tucna**, could be linked to tučno, fat in Slavic...
 Anus: **cuzdo**, could be linked to gaz, anus in Bulgarian, from Burushaski skus, anus
 Tongue/langue: **jectis**, linked to jazik, tongue (Slavic), jezik (BSCM), from egtis (PIE), jungus (Bur), tongue
 Forehead/front: **talo**, linked to čelo, forehead in old Slavic and BSCM, from talay, head in Dravidian
 Heart/cœur: **kridyo**, linked to srdce (c. sl., BSCM), from PIE kert, Drav hrdro, Sanskrit hrd, heart, TE kerda
 Blood/sang: **croeso**, linked to krov, blood in Russian, krv in BSCM, from krews (PIE), krav (Drav), kura (TE)
 Skin/peau: **cuda**, linked to koža, skin in common Slavic and BSCM, would come from the Sanskrit koša
 Back/dos: **akrestia**, linked to krast in Bulgarian and krsta in BSCM
 Throat/gorge: **guesia**, linked to guša in Bulgarian and BSCM
 Health/santé: **slano**, linked to slan, cured in BSCM and celenie, healthcare in Bulgarian
 Illness/maladie: **balo**, linked to bol, pain (c. sl., Kartv), vali, hurt (Drav), bal, be ill (Bur), bahli, hurt (TE)
 Cough/toux: **kuso**, linked to kašel in c. sl., kašalj in BSCM, cough, khos in Burushaski, cough
 Pus: **goru**, linked to the Bulgarian gur, pus

Numbers, linked to Slavic and Lithuanian, coming from Indo-European and Sanskrit:

One/un: **oinos**, ena (Glozel), linked to vienas in Lithuanian and eno in Slovenian, from Drav onn, Bur hen, and first, **remos**, linked to pre, in front in Serbian, the p falling in Gaulish, arima, one in Scythian, purme (Bur)
 Two/deux: **duo**, linked to dva (c. sl., Sanskrit), da (Hittite); **allos**, second, linked to altan, two (Burushaski)
 Three/trois: **tri**, similar to the c. sl., Sanskrit, Hittite, Tokharian; third, **tritros**, linked to treti (c. sl.), treći (BSCM)
 Four/quatre: **petuar**, linked to kietury en Lithuanian, the p replacing the k in Gaulish, četiri in BSCM
 Five/cinq: **pempe**, linked to pet (Bosnian), fifth **pimpetos**, same root, linked to Sanskrit, Avestan, Hittite panca, Dravidian ancu with loss of p, Burushaski cendo
 Six: **swech** in Celtic, linked to šest in common Slavic and in BSCM, sad in Dravidian, six in Hittite, Avestan
 Seven/sept: **sait** in Celtic, linked to sedem in several Slavic languages and sedam in BSCM, satua in Hittite
 Eight/huit, **oxto** in Gaulish, pronounced okhto, linked to osem in Slavic, osam in BSCM, ettu in Dravidian

Names of colours:

Red/rouge: **rudos**, from rudy, red (Czech), rid, reddish (BSCM), rudhros, red (PIE) arattam (Drav), bardum (Bur), may also be linked to Sumerian urudu, copper
 Blue/bleu: **livo**, linked to sliva, plum in c. sl., sleiwos in PIE, Gaulish loosing the s, maybe Kartvelian kliavi
 Blue-green/bleu-vert: **glaston**, linked to zelen in Bulgarian, BSCM, ghlastos in PIE, giltir in Burushaski
 White/blanc: **balaros**, linked to belo, white (c. sl.), from bhlaros, white (PIE), val, white (Drav), barom (Bur)
 Whiteness/blancheur: **balio**, linked to belo, white in c. sl., from bhlaros in PIE, val in Drav, bel, barom in Bur
 Black/noir: **dubus**, linked to dim, smoke in c. sl. (smoked, hence blackened), dumas in Bur, dhubnos in PIE

Grey/gris: **letos**, also meaning aged, linked to ljetto, year in c. sl., may come from paraitu, aged in Dravidian
Yellow/jaune: **gelo, givos**, linked to zelt (Bulgarian), žut (BSCM), ghltnos (PIE), giltir (Bur), ghilu, shine (TE)

Words linked to cold and heat:

Snow/neige: **snig**, linked to snieg in common Slavic, snijeg in BSCM, from sneighs in PIE, sina in TE
Ice/glacé: **iegis**, linked to led, ice in c. sl., iegis in PIE, giye, snow in Bur, would come from proto-Uralic jeng
Snow/neige: **ladgo**, is linked to the same roots
Heat/chaleur: **tepes**, linked to teplo, hot (c. sl.), toplo (BSCM), tepis, hot (Vinča), tep (Kartv), ted (Dravidian)
Animal heat/chaleur animale: **lato**, ljet in c. sl., linked to lato, summer in Polish, ljetto, summer in c. sl., BSCM
Hot/chaud: **gormo**, from goriatchi, hot (Russian), gorjeti, burn (BSCM), gher (PIE), greh (Drav), garum (Bur)

Words linked to knowledge linked to the c. sl. veda, science, linked with Sanskrit veda and Drav vidvas:

Wisdom, wiseman/sagesse, sage: **veda, vedos**, linked to veda, wisdom, vedec, wiseman (Slovenian), vittia (Vinča), wisdom, vadhyar, teacher, vidvas, educated man in Dravidian
Knowledge/connaissance: **vedio, suvidias**, veda (Glozel), linked to vednost, knowledge (Serbian), veda, science (Czech), vadhyar, teacher, vidvas, educated man in Dravidian
Seer, prophet/devin, prophète: **vatis**, linked to vještac, wizard (BSCM), **vidlua**, witch, **wedya**, prayer

Words linked to power and war:

Gaulish/Gaulois: **Gal**, linked to gala, powerful (Glozel), Old Slavonic golema, powerful, Bulgarian golemeja se, be proud, golemec, powerful person, BSCM golem, giant, from PIE galnos, power and kali, hero (Drav)
Glory/gloire: **clavo, livo**, kalve (Glozel) linked to slava, glory (c. sl.), c replacing s in Gaulish, klewos in PIE
Celt/Celte: **Kelt**, linked to **clouto**, glorious (klutos in PIE), derived from **clavo**, glory, kalve in Glozelian, slava in c. sl., or **kaletto**, hard, hero, linked to Bulgarian kalen, from PIE kaletos, hard and kali, hero in Dravidian
Chief/chef: **cen, penno**, linked to kan in old Bulgarian, pan in Polish and Czech, kon, chief in Dravidian; cen means head in Dravidian, as pen, **penno** in Gaulish, also meaning God in Dravidian, which could have given his name to the God Pan, revered by Dravidians and Gauls, in particular in present day Crimea.
Chief/chef: **connos**, linked to kan, chief in Bulgarian and Altaic, knez, prince in BSCM, kon, chief in Dravidian
Chief/chef: **brennos**, linked to barin in Russian, master or Lord
Chief/chef: **vlatos**, vela (Glozel) linked to vladar, leader (BSCM), vlast, power (c. sl.), vel, chief in Dravidian
Commandant: **vellaunos**, vela (Glozel), linked to vladar, leader (BSCM), vlast, power (c. sl.), vel (Dravidian), vali, great, honoured, glorified (Hittite), walo, king (Tocharian)
Sovereign/souverain: **valos**, linked to vela, chief (Glozel), vladar, sovereign (BSCM), vel, king, chief (Drav)
Master/maître: **valo**, vela (Glozel), linked to balen, master (Thracian), veljak, master (Slovenian), vel (Drav)
Power/puissance: **vlatto**, vela (Glozel), linked to vlast, power (c. sl.), PIE wehl, lead and Dravidian val, strong
Preside/présider: **versed**, meaning sitting over, linked to predsjedati, preside in BSCM
Justice: **viroionia**, linked to verit, trust, vjerovati in BSCM, from the PIE weros, Bur warc, true
Loyalty/loyauté: **virido**, linked to verit, trust, vjerovati se, trust each other in BSCM, from PIE weros, Bur warc
Loi: **kanis**, linked to zakon, law in Slavic and BSCM, or to kaznit, punish in Slavic
Servant, vassal/serviteur, vassal: **vassos**, linked to the BSCM vazal
Assembly/assemblée: **comboro**, linked to sabor (BSCM), kampala (Drav), kaa bar (Bur), sambhara (Sanskrit)
Assembly/assemblée: **comrato** or **rato**, linked to rada, assembly in Ukrainian
Assembly/assemblée: **samonios**, linked to sejm, assembly in Polish, and samanam, assembly in Sanskrit
Truth/vérité: **virotus**, linked to the root vjero of vjerovatno, plausible, from the PIE weros
People/peuple: **teuta**, tauta (Glozel), linked to the God Teutates, Teta (Glozel), teuta, people in PIE and Illyrian, teuto (Vinča), tanda, tod, crowd in Dravidian, tjuđe in Thracian and old Bulgarian, from which would come ljudi, people in c. sl., may be linked to **lidos**, crowd (Gaulish), from PIE lewd, people
Victory/victoire: **budi**, linked to pobeda, victory in Russian, pobjeda in BSCM
Warrior/soldat: **katos**, linked to četnik, warrior (Bulgarian), četa, brigade (BSCM, Slovenian), kanta (Drav)
Combatant/combattant: **rakatos**, linked to the same roots, from katos, raukos, hard in PIE, kanta in Dravidian
Battle/bataille: **katu**, linked to the same roots, kotora, combat (Russian), bitka, battle (BSCM), to Dravidian kadu, make war, katti, sword, kadi, wound and patay, battle, Akkadian maqatu, attack and Hittite katu, strife
Fort: **kater**, linked to kata, camp (Old Bulgarian), katun of Vlasi (BSCM), kottay, fort (Drav), kadu, fort (Akkadian), kotah, fort (Sanskrit), kastro, fort (Etruscan)
Combat/combattre: **batu**, linked to biti, beat (Scythian), bit, beat (c. sl.), biti (BSCM), pattu (Drav), bet (Elamite)
Combat: **battu**, linked to bit, beat in sl. c., bitka, battle (BSCM), pattu, beat (Drav), bhata in Sanskrit, bet (Elam)
Group, troop/groupe, troupe: **ceterna**, linked to četa, brigade (BSCM, Slovenian), katu (Drav), hit (Elamite)
Group/groupe: **corio**, linked to hor (BSCM), hora (Bulgarian), group, korjos (PIE), hol (Bur), army, kuran, defense line (Bur), karas, army (Hittite), karasu, army (Akkadian), goru, army (Persian)
Armed unit/unité armée: **drungos**, linked to drunga, armed unit in old Bulgarian, družina, band, company in Croatian, band, troop in Bosnian, family in Slovenian, from the PIE dreughō
Troup/troupe: **slugo**, linked to sluga, servant in common Slavic and BSCM, from sloughos in PIE
Gladius sword/glaive: **cladibo**, from kaliča (Bulgarian), kljewos (PIE), katti (Drav), kladivo, hammer (c. sl.)

Words linked to religion:

God/Dieu: **Devos**, Divos (Glozel), linked to c. sl. deva, djeva, virgin, Deivo, Deiva (Vinča), devu (Dravidian)
God/Dieu: **Mogetios, Mogon**, linked to mogući, almighty (BSCM), mogho, power (PIE), magado (Dravidian)
Baco, God revered in Chalon sur Saone, linked to Bog, God in c. sl., Bago in Scythian, Bhaga in Drav, Sanskrit
Belenos: important Gaulish God, linked to the Slavic God Belebog, Velinas in Lithuanian, linked to vel in Drav
Lug: one of the most important Gaulish Gods, also revered by Serbians, whose name is linked to luč, light in Slavic, velicham in Drav, balichom in Bur, luk in Elam, Hittite. 30 names of Gaulish Gods are linked to Slavic.

Mountain/montagne: **perkunio**, linked to perkunas (Lithuanian), perkunjom (PIE), to the Slavic God Perun, Perune in Kalash, to **erkos**, oak forest in Gaulish, to the mythic Hercynian Forest of the Gauls, which name could come from Drav perkuni, grow (for trees), giving credit to the Dravidian origin of the Gaulish religion.

Holy forest/foret sacrée: **drunemeton**, holy forest of Galati, could come from daru, wood (Thracian), linked to drvo, derevo (c. sl.), and **nemo**, linked to nebo, sky (c. sl.), or deru, wood, nemeton, sanctuary (PIE), or Der, God, vanam, forest, sky, mountain, holy forest in Drav, with loss of the va in Gaulish. The fact that the name of several wooded mountains comes from vanam (Morvan in France, Van in Switzerland), as Dravidian holy mountains Vindhya in India, which would have given their name to mount Vindius (or Vinnius) in Asturia (Spain), where Pline already places the Indian tribe Bolinges (he also names Telugus Trilinges), and to **vidua**, forest in Gaulish, gives credit to this Dravidian etymology, coherent with the Dravidian origin of the Gaulish religion. Dravidians would be at the origin of the cult of the tree. Pre-Celtic Glozelians prayed Jana, Goddess of the Forest, ancestor of the Roman Diana. Even the French word foret could come from poril in Drav

Holy/sacré: **noibo**, from nebo, sky (c. sl.), nap, God (Elam) **nemo**, sky, vanam, sky (Drav), nepis, sky (Hittite)

Druid/druides: **drui**, from daru, tree, vid, see (Thracian), drvo, tree, vidjet, see (c. sl.), Der, God, vid, see (Drav)

Sacrifice: **odberto**, linked to **od**, from, and **beru**, take, in c. sl. and to ida, give in sacrifice in Glozelian

Exalt, revere/louer, vénérer: **mol**, mola (Glozel), linked to moliti, pray (BSCM), maybe moli, speak in Drav

Praise, prayer/louange, prière: **malo**, **molatus**, mlatio (Glozel) linked to molitva, prayer (BSCM), moli (Drav)

Glorify/glorifier: **moleio**, linked to the same roots, from PIE moldhos, prayer, maybe moli, speak in Dravidian

Words linked to time:

Day/jour: **diio**, **din** linked to den in c. sl., dan in BSCM, from dinos in PIE, din in Drav, Sanskrit, den in Bur

Evening/soir: **ucher**, **veskero** in Celtic, linked to večer in common Slavic and BSCM, from wespros in PIE

Night/nuit: **nox** (pronounced nokh) or **nocs**, linked to noć in c. sl. and BSCM, noṭi in PIE, maxa in Dravidian

Now/maintenant: **nu**, linked to nu (Russian, BSCM), no (Polish), nu (PIE), nana (Drav) muu (Bur), nu (Hittite)

Day/journée: **lat**, linked to ljetu, variable period of time according to languages, from latom in PIE

Today/aujourd'hui: **sindidiu** or **se divos**, linked to segodnia, today in Russian, djeu in PIE, sid, day in Drav

Yesterday/hier: **gdesi**, linked to Polish gdzies, in former times

Period of time/période de temps: **remessos**, linked to vrijeme (BSCM), vremena (Russian), time, with loss of v

Month/mois: **mid**, mana (Glozelian), linked to miesiac (c. sl.), mjesec (BSCM), mez (Abkhaz), masan (Drav)

Year/année: **bletho**, linked to ljetu, year in common Slavic and in BSCM

Winter/hiver: **giamos**, from zima (c. sl., BSCM), ghjemos (PIE), gil, cold (Alt), giye, snow (Bur), gima (Hittite)

Autumn/automne: **autumnos**, from tama (Glozel), **dumno**, dark, temno (c. sl.), tamno (BSCM), dumas (Bur)

Summer/été: **samos**, would be linked to očen, jesen, autumn in Slavic, and sinni, summer in Burushaski

Spring/printemps: **vesna**, linked to vesna (c. sl.), Goddess of Spring, from wesenos (PIE), vaa (Dravidian)

Words linked to work and occupation:

Worker/travailleur: **arat**, kara (Glozel), linked to ratay, worker (Bulgarian) radnik, worker (BSCM), Scythian arei, ploughman, PIE dratis, work, drator, worker, Altaic ar, Bur har and Dravidian uravan, farmer

Smith/forgeron: **gobantion**, linked to c. sl. and BSCM kovač, kowal in Polish, kebed in Avar, kol in Dravidian

Smithy/forge: **gobali**, linked to the same roots, kovačnica in BSCM

Doctor/médecin: **legis**, linked to lekar, doctor in Slavic and BSCM, lečit, cure in Slavic

Servant/serviteur: **adbero**, derived from **beru**, take, linked to brat, take in c. sl., from PIE ad and bher

Servant/serviteur: **slugo**, linked to sluga, servant in common Slavic, from slougho in PIE

Words linked to everyday life:

House/maison: **demo**, linked to c. sl. dom, house, home (BSCM), demos (PIE), dama (Sanskrit), daman (Avestan), domate (Burushaski)

Hut/hutte: **buta**, linked to budka, hut in Bulgarian, from bhut, dwelling in PIE, bitu, house in Dravidian

Hut/hutte: **barga**, linked to old Slavic borg, roof on 4 pillars, Polish brog and Czech brh

Roof, shelter/toit, abri: **kleta**, from kleta, cellar (BSCM), house, hut (c. sl.), Drav kuti, house, Bur kutu, TE kuta

Shelter/abri: **krovos**, linked to krov, roof in BSCM and Slavic, would be linked to the Dravidian kir, cover

Closed place/lieu clos: **gorto**, linked to gorod (Russian), grad (BSCM), city, from gordhos (PIE), koritu (Drav), kurta, town (Hittite), kirtu, citadel (Akkadian), gordum, town (Phrygian)

Village: **trebo**, linked to old Sl. trem, Russian terem, village, threbo, dwelling (PIE), tharbai, pile of stones (Bur)

Dwelling/habitation: **vastu**, linked to ves, village (Czech, Slovak), vis (Sanskrit), vas, dwell (Drav)

Resident/résident: **adsedo**, linked to sjudioč, resident in BSCM, from sidet, sit in c. sl., sedos, residence in PIE

Door/porte: **dvoro**, linked to dver, door in Russian, dveri in BSCM, dvara in Sanskrit, tora, open in Dravidian

Corner/coin: **kut**, linked to kut in BSCM and Czech, kat in Bulgarian, kat in Polish, from the PIE kant, corner

Table: **stalo**, linked to stol, table in c. sl. and Bosnian, from stolos in PIE, tol in Dravidian, which gave dolmen

Coal/charbon: **gluuo**, **gluvo**, linked to ugol, coal in Russian, ugalj in BSCM, my come from gol, burn in Bur

Light/lumière: **lukno**, from luč (c. sl.), leuks (PIE), velitchna (Drav), balichom (Bur), luk (Elam, Hittite), luks, illuminate (Tocharian)

Axe/hache: **biion** linked to bit, beat in common Slavic, biti in BSCM, pattu in Dravidian

Pen/stylo: **brukos**, linked to ruka, hand in common Slavic, eraka in Dravidian, rukopis, manuscript in c. sl.

Bed/lit: **legio**, linked to ležat, ležet, lie down in common Slavic, ležati in BSCM, from leghejo in PIE

Fire/feu: **aedu**, linked to ad, hell (Bulgarian), Aedui (from **aidwos**, ardent, aedo in Glozelian) Aedii, Thracian tribe ancestor of Aedui according to P. Serafimov, from ater (PIE), which gave vatra, fire (BSCM, Romanian, Czech), âtre (French), linked to vata, home in Drav, aidho, burn (PIE), odi, heat in Drav, ot, fire (Alt, Turkish)

Bed/lit: **legio**, linked to ležat, ležet, lie down in common Slavic, ležati in BSCM, from leghejo in PIE

Basket/panier: **kista**, linked to koš, basket (c. sl., BSCM), kesa, bag (BSCM), kasjo (Vinča), kista, basket (PIE)

Clog, boot/galoche, botte: **kaluga**, linked to kalosza, boot in Polish, kaloše, clogs in BSCM

Coat/manteau: **brato**, linked to vretište, garment (Bulgarian), bat, sheepskin (Bur), epartu, coat (Akkadian)

Cape: **gobano**, linked to kabat, coat in Czech, kaput, coat in BSCM, from the Dravidian kappu, cover

Cloth/toile: **lotna**, linked to plotno, cloth in c. sl., platno in BSCM, **lino**, woollen coat in Gaulish, derived from **wlana**, wool (Gaulish), vlna, wool (sl. c.), vuna (BSCM), ulana (Sanskrit, Hittite), philam, woollen cloth (Bur)
 Cellar/cave: **cauna**, could be linked to konoba, inn in BSCM and would come from kaiva, cellar in Dravidian
 Rope/corde: **segno**, linked to sukno, rope in Bulgarian and cloth in BSCM
 Chain/chaine: **reigo**, linked to veriga in Bulgarian and Slovenian, from reigo, link in PIE
 Crock/Pot: **krokano**, linked to kračaga (Bulgarian), krčag, pitcher, krčma, inn (BSCM), kurky, pot in Drav, kurkurru, pot in Akkadian
 Ball/balle: **glavom**, linked to glava, head in Slavic and in BSCM
 Stick/bâton: **matigon**, linked to Russian motyka, motika in BSCM, matoki in Georgian and PIE mat
 Dirt/saleté: **muso**, linked to musor, waste (Russian), linked to makku, dirt (Drav), mos, mud flood (Bur)

Words linked to means of transport:

Boat/navire: **lougá**, linked to lodka, barque in Slavic, lađa, name of an old boat in BSCM, roka in Sanskrit
 Vehicle/véhicule: **vegnos**, linked to vozilo, vehicle (BSCM), vahitra (Old Indian), vandi (Drav.), wag (Hurrian)
 Wheel/roue: **koros, kolo**, linked to kolo, wheel (c. sl.), kel (PIE), kal, chariot (Drav), larokores, round (Bur), from TE kola, round
 2-wheel chariot/char à 2 roues: **kolisato**, from kolo, wheel (c. sl.), kočija, kolica (BSCM), kal, chariot (Drav)
 Chariot: **polo**, linked to the same roots with transformation of k in p in Gaulish, from Dravidian pul, chariot
 Chariot: **carruca**, from karuča (Bulgarian), karoca (BSCM), kers (PIE), karun (Bur), kal (Drav), kurra (Hittite)
 Chariot/char: **carri**, linked to kara (Czech), karoca (BSCM), kers (PIE), karun, move (Bur), kal (Drav)
 Two-place chariot/char à deux places: **essedum**, fom sedo, sit in common Slavic

Auxiliary words:

Who/qui: **pos**, kas (Glozel), from ko (BSCM), p replacing k, qos (PIE), ka (Altaic), ke (Bur), aka (Elam), ko (TE)
 Whoever/quiconque: **nepos**, also in Glozelian, linked to neko in BSCM, the p replacing the k in Gaulish, from neqos in PIE, ke in Burushaski. By the way, the sound k came back in French in qui and quiconque.
 Negation/négation: **ne**, similar to c. sl. negation, from PIE ne, no, linked to Bur ne...ne, neither...nor, na (TE)
 No/non: **ni**, linked to nie, no in c. sl., from ne, no (PIE) - Yes/oui: **to** in Glozelian Gaulish, linked to da (c. sl.)
 Before/avant: **ris**, from prije, pre, before in BSCM, from peru, big (Drav), purme, before (Bur), pra (Sanskrit)
 Right/à droite: **dexsiuo, dessu**, linked to desno (BSCM, Slovenian), dexsi (PIE), daksina (Drav, Sanskrit)
 Left/à gauche: **laibos**, linked to levo, ljevo in common Slavic and in BSCM, from laiwo in PIE
 And/et: **a**, one of the words meaning and in common Slavic, may be linked to ka in Burushaski
 I, to me/je, moi, à moi: **mi**, dative in c. sl, **sme**, linked to sam (BSCM), mi (TE), **sve**, linked to svojo, sue in Bur, sva in Sanskrit, sa in TE, **moy**, linked to moy, my, from PIE, mi, my in Burushaski
 Thou/tu: **ti** in Celtic, identical to common Slavic and BSCM, from tu in PIE, ti in TE
 Your/ton: **to**, linked to tvojo, your in common Slavic and BSCM, from PIE and Sanskrit tva
 We/nous: **mu**, linked to mi, we (c. sl., BSCM, Bur.), ma (TE), **ve**, you (Glozel), linked to vi, you (c. sl.), wa (Bur)
 Many/beaucoup: **menneki**, linked to mnogo, many (c. sl.), menegh (PIE), mikka (Drav), meki (Hittite), man (Altaic), manga (TE)
 All/tout: **ciallos**, linked to cjal, all (Bulgarian), cio, cjel (BSCM), cel (Slovenian), koilus in PIE, khol in Bur
 From/de: **es**, linked to iz, from in Russian, BSCM and Slovenian
 Between/entre: **medio**, linked to među in BSCM, među in Russian and Bulgarian, between, from PIE medios
 Over/dessus: **ver**, linked to Bulgarian varhu, over, Russian verkh, Slovak and Bosnian vrh, from Drav varay
 Near/près de: **okk**, linked to oko in BSCM, okolo in common Slavic, near, maybe from rakkukan in Dravidian
 Under/sous: **vo**, ipa in Glozelian, linked to pod in Slavic, the v replacing the p in Gaulish, from upo in PIE
 To/vers: **do**, linked to do, to in common Slavic and in BSCM, may be linked to the TE locative particle da
 To/vers: **ko**, linked to k, ko, to in common Slavic and in BSCM, may be linked to the TE locative particle ka
 Superlative/superlatif: **samo, sama**, similar to the Russian superlative and to sam, very in Burushaski
 Same/le même: **samal-isto**, linked to samo, isto, same (c. sl.), samo-isto (BSCM), samo (PIE), samam (Drav.)
 As/comme: **samalo**, same root, from PIE samo, Dravidian samam, linked to zamalo, almost in BSCM
 This/ceci: **emo**, ea in Glozelian, linked to evo, this is (BSCM), eno (PIE), emma (Dravidian), ama (Kartvelian)
 That/cela: **ta** in Glozelian Gaulish, linked to taj, that in BSCM, ta, that in Vinča speech, te, that in Bur, ta in TE
 Both/tous les deux: **ambi**, linked to abi in Thracian, ambu in Drav, ambo in Bur, oba in Slavic and BSCM, both

Various words:

Name/nom: **anmen**, linked to nama in Glozelian, meno, name in c. sl., ime in BSCM, from the PIE nomen
 Darkness/obscurité: **temello**, linked to temnota, tama, darkness (c. sl., BSCM), tamra (Drav), tumtan (Bur)
 Debt/dette: **dulgo** or **dulgiton**, linked to dolg, debt in Russian, dug, debt in BSCM, from dhleghla in PIE
 Thought/pensée: **menman**, linked to mnenie (Russian), mijenje (BSCM), men (Vinča), man, thought (Drav)
 Opinion: **meno**, linked to mnenie, opinion (Russian), mijenje, opinion (BSCM), man, thought (Dravidian)
 Judgment/jugement: **messi**, linked to Slavic myšlenie, mišljenje in BSCM, opinion
 Joy/joie: **veso**, linked to vesolo, cheerful in Slavic, veselje, joy in BSCM, assus, joy in Burushaski
 Rage: **vecó**, linked to bes in Bulgarian and bijes, anger in BSCM, vitay, fury in Dravidian
 Rage, fury/fureur: **buryon**, linked to buria, storm in c. sl., Drav bura, burka, noise of blowing wind, Bur burui
 Murmur/murmure: **dordo**, linked to Bulgarian dardorja, murmur, from the PIE drdajo, Dravidian dardarn
 Friend/ami: **rios**, linked to Slavic priatelj, Bosnian prijatelj, the p falling in Gaulish, from PIE prijos, dear
 Comrade/camarade: **combratir**, linked to brat, brother in slave, from Dravidian kum and PIE bhrater
 Union: **veriugon**, linked to verit, trust, vjerovati se, trust each other in BSCM, and maybe jugom, yoke
 Dream/song: **sounos**, linked to son in common Slavic, dream, sanjati, to dream in BSCM, from supno in PIE
 Part/partie: **dalio**, from djal (Bulgarian), dio (BSCM), del (Slovenian), part, dal, part (Sanskrit), del, cut (Bur)
 Religious feast/fête religieuse: **litu**, linked to likovati, feast (BSCM), lessu, religious feast (Dravidian), assus (Burushaski), essa, feast (Hittite), issunua, feast (Akkadian)
 Point/pointe: **banna**, linked to bonela, fork in Bulgarian
 Trip/voyage: **podo**, linked to putovanje, trip in BSCM, pent, road in PIE, put in BSCM, pogu in Dravidian

Surface: **talamos**, linked to tela (Glozel), tilo, surface, tlo, soil (c. sl.), tala, earth (Sanskrit), talam, dol (Drav)
 Life/vie, existence: **bitu**, **buti**, buion (Glozel), linked to bitje, life (Bulgarian, Slovenian), biće (BSCM), bhuti (Sanskrit), Drav putu, come to life, to existence, Bur ba, exist, also linked to bitos, immortal, eternal in Glozelian
 World, universe/monde, univers: **bitu**, linked to c. sl. bit, biti in BSCM, be, putu in Dravidian, ba, exist (Bur)
 Being, creature/être, créature: **bivos**, linked to the same roots as the two previous words
 Desire/désir: **clani**, linked to želja, čežnja, desire in BSCM
 Fear/peur: **boto**, linked to c. sl. boitsia, fear, bojati se in BSCM, bhi, bhajate in Sanskrit
 Answer/réponse: **atepos**, linked to odpoved, answer in Czech, atake, answer in Abkhazian
 Tomb/tombeau: **logan**, linked to ležat, ležet, lie down in c. sl., ležati in BSCM
 Gold/or: **goltam**, linked to the common Slavic zoloto, zlato, gold, from the PIE ghltom, Bur. giltir, shine
 Birth/naissance: **berreton**, linked to Czech and BSCM porod, from **beru**, peru, birth in Dravidian
 Marvel/merveille: **coudi**, linked to čudan in BSCM and cudowny in Polish, marvelous, kuus in Bur, magic
 Tower/tour: **keliknon**, linked to kula, tower in BSCM, from PIE keliknom, Dravidian kula, fortress
 Love/amour: **lubi**, linked to ljubov in Russian, ljubav in BSCM, love, from the PIE lubjo, love
 Burning heat/chaleur brulante, passion: **gratu**, linked to grjet, heat in c. sl., gorjeti in BSCM, greh in Dravidian
 Kiss/baiser: **bust**, linked to buži in Polish, pusa in Czech and BSCM, kiss, from bhusajo, to kiss in PIE
 Language/langage: **iaxti**, linked to jazik in Slavic, jezik in BSCM, language, PIE egtis, Drav ian, Bur jungus
 Crowd/foule: **lidos**, linked to ljudi (c. sl., BSCM), people, lao, people in Glozelian, from PIE lugtos, multitude
 Profit: **sukoro**, linked to korist, profit in Slavic and BSCM
 Burden/fardeau: **trodma**, linked to trud, hard work, effort (Bulgarian, Russian), trudnoca, pregnancy (BSCM)
 Strength, power/force, pouvoir: **nertos**, from nara, man (Thracian), nara (Scythian), nerez, male animal (Bulgarian), nertos, strength (PIE), an, man (Drav), inara, vigor (Hittite), najra, man (TE)
 Aspect: **vida**, linked to vida in Glozelian, vid in Slavic, aspect, from videt, see, from PIE weid and Sanskrit vid
 Thief/voleur: **tati**, linked to old Slavic, Slovenian and BSCM tat, thief, may come from Dravidian tirutan, thief

Adjectives:

Clear/clair: **argio**, linked to jarki (Serbian, Russian), jarak (Bulgarian), yaari (Bur), uru (Drav), arka (Sanskrit) sunlight, jara, clear (TE), may come from hargin, dragon (Bur) and have given **argentum**, silver in Gaulish
 Brave: **art**, linked to rat, war (BSCM), ratha, war chariot (Glozelian), could come from ar, noble (Drav), ardu, soldier (Akkadian)
 Dark/sombre: **dumno**, **temis**, **temelos**, from temno (c. sl.), tamno (BSCM), dark, tima, dumas (Thracian, Bur), tem (Scythian), temos (PIE), tamra (Drav), dim, smoke (c. sl., BSCM), dhumnos (PIE), teman (Elam), tuma (TE)
 Deep/profond: **dubno**, linked to duboko, deep in BSCM, dhubus in PIE
 Thin/fin: **tanos**, linked to tenki, thin in Russian, tanak in BSCM, from the PIE tenus, Bur thaanium, long
 New/nouveau: **novios**, linked to novy, nov (c. sl., BSCM), newos (PIE), nav (Sanskrit), newas (Hittite)
 True/vrai: **veros**, linked to the root vjero of vjerovatno, plausible in BSCM, from weros in PIE, warc in Bur
 Silent/silencieux: **tauso**, takha in Glozelian, linked to tichy, silent in c. sl., tiši in BSCM, tausos in PIE
 Big/grand: **maros**, linked to maros (Thracian), mera (Slavon), mahan (Sanskrit), marru (Drav), marin (Bur), magari (Kartv)
 Great man/grand homme: **maroviros**, linked to two Old Slavic words, mera and vyras, Drav marru and vir
 Big/grand: **balco**, linked to velik (Bulgarian, BSCM, Slovenian), bolshoy (Russian), bel (PIE), bal, grow (Drav)
 Fair/juste: **viroiono**, linked to verit, trust, vjerovati in BSCM, from weros in PIE, warc in Burushaski
 Loyal: **viros**, linked to verit, trust, vjerovati se, trust each other in BSCM, from weros in PIE, warc in Burushaski
 Best/meilleur: **velio**, linked to bolje, best in BSCM, from bedjos in PIE, vel in Dravidian
 Dead/mort: **marvos**, linked to mrtav, dead (BSCM), PIE mrtos, mrvos, Indo-Iranian Mara, demon of Death (also in Glozelian and Slavic), margu, dead (Drav), mara, death (Sanskrit), mar (Hittite), mara, die in PE
 Bloody/sanglant: **crovos**, linked to krov, blood in c. sl., krv in BSCM, from krews in PIE, krav in Dravidian
 Cruel: **craudio**, also linked to krov, blood in c. sl., krv in BSCM, from krews in PIE, krav in Dravidian
 Beaten/battu: **gano**, linked to gnati, beat in Old Bulgarian, may come from gan, be wounded in Burushaski
 Full/plein: **lano**, linked to pleno, full (c. sl.), p falling in Gaulish, ulano, fil in Glozelian, from PIE pleno
 Alive/vivant: **bivos**, bitos in Glozelian, linked to živi, alive in c. sl., živ in BSCM, gihwo in PIE, ba, ji (Bur.)
 Clear/clair: **asno**, **jessinos**, linked to jasno, clear in c. sl., Bulgarian and BSCM, asenya in Sanskrit
 Last/dernier: **ostimos**, linked to ostatak, last part in Bulgarian, ostalo in BSCM, from postmos in PIE
 Good, rejoicing/bon, réjouissant: **vesu**, from veselo, rejoicing (c. sl.), veseo (BSCM), assus (Burushaski)
 Young/jeune: **ioin**, linked to iuna (Slavon), **iovanti**, from Venetian iuvants, PIE juwon, Drav jovu, Bur jua, son
 Hot/chaud: **vritu**, **gritu**, from vroč, hot, gret, heat (Slovenian), vruč, grijeti (BSCM), greh (Drav), garum (Bur)
 Glorious/glorieux: **cluto**, klutos in PIE, linked to clavo, glory, slava in c. sl., could be at the origin of Celt
 High/haut: **agranio**, linked to gore, mountainous in Bulgarian, at the top in BSCM, gori, high in Dravidian
 High/haut: **ardus**, could be linked to rid, high point in Bulgarian and to kara, high in Dravidian
 Furious/furieux: **baran**, from buren (Bulgarian), buran (BSCM), stormy, bura, wind noise (Drav), burui (Bur), from TE bura, storm
 Furious/furieux: **luto**, linked to ljut, furious in Slovenian, Bulgarian and BSCM, from Burushaski latet, frown
 Rapid/rapide: **bruios**, linked to brz, rapid in Czech and BSCM, barz, rapid in Bulgarian, from Sanskrit bhra
 Slow/lent: **mallo**, **mergio**, can be linked to medleno in Russian and po malo, slowly in BSCM
 Aged/agé: **letos**, linked to ljeto, year in c. sl. and BSCM, from leto in PIE, paraito, pala, aged in Dravidian
 Weak/faible: **cleio**, linked to keljav in Bulgarian, slab in BSCM
 Strong/fort: **crip**, linked to krepak in Bulgarian, Slovenian and BSCM, from krepas in PIE
 Strong/fort: **acu**, slinked to jak, strong in Slovenian, Bulgarian and BSCM, from the PIE ac
 Hard, hero/dur, héros: **caleto**, linked to kalen, hard (Bulgarian), kaletu (PIE), kali (Drav), could give **Kelt**, Celt
 Hard/dur: **craudio**, from korav, hard (Bulgarian), krut, hard (BSCM, Slovenian), krutas (PIE), kuruti (Drav)
 Healthy/en bonne santé: **iaccos**, ieca (Glozel), linked to jak, strong (Bulgarian, Slovenian, BSCM), PIE jekos
 Mighty/puissant: **mogeti**, linked to mogast, (Bulgarian), mogući (BSCM), magadan (Serbian), magado (Drav)

Great/grand: **magos**, maga in Glazelian, can be linked to the same roots, from magado, brave, king in Drav
 Noble: **magalo**, linked to magota, noble (Bulgarian), moguci (BSCM), maq (Abkhazian), magado (Dravidian)
 Pregnant/enceinte: **beranto**, from beru, peru, birth (Drav), beremennaia, pregnant (Russian), brena (BSCM), pera, give birth (TE)
 Short/court: **kerto**, linked to kratki, korotki, short in c. sl., kratak in BSCM, kuru in Drav, kura in TE
 Expensive/cher: **druto**, can be linked to drogi, drag, drahy, expensive in Polish, BSCM and Czech
 Fat/gras, gros: **smeru**, from smer, fat, linked to Polish smar, far, from PIE smerus
 Transparent: **glano**, linked to glasnost, transparency in Russian
 Soft/mou: **leino**, can be linked to lenivy, lazy in c. sl., lijen in BSCM, leni, weak in PIE, len, quiet in Bur
 Lazy/paresseux: **lisco**, can be linked to the same roots, linked to len, quiet, peaceful, motionless in Burushaski
 Naked/nu: **noxto** (pronounced nokhto) linked to nahy in Czech, nagy, nag in BSCM, from nocados in PIE
 Sweet/sucré: **suado**, can be linked to sladki in Slavic, sladak in BSCM, sweet, from PIE swadus
 First, supreme/premier, suprême: **veramus**, linked to arima (Scythian) alem (Bulgarian), **ver**, over, linked to verkh (Russian) vrh (BSCM), summit, from PIE vers, Dravidian varay (high), peru (big), Bur. beru, Altaic vara, TE bara, big

NB: c. sl.: common Slavic; Old sl.: Old Slavic; PIE: Proto-Indo-European; Drav: Dravidian; Kartv: Kartvelian; Alt: Altaic; BSCM: Bosnian-Serbian-Croatian-Montenegrin; Bur: Burushaski; Elam: Elamite; TE: Trans-Eurasian; Gaulish: in **bold letters**

APPENDIX 2

- aller/go: the irregular conjugation of aller may come from the Dravidian verbs alay, va and ir
- venir/come: close to va, come in Dravidian
- arriver/arrive: close to aruvu, come near in Dravidian
- aimer/love: very close to the Dravidian amar, love
- être/be: close to iru (pronounced itru), be in Dravidian
- porter/carry: close to the Dravidian poru, carry
- payer/pay: very close to the Dravidian pay, pay
- tirer/pull: close to the Dravidian words tira, open a door, iru, pull
- murmurer/murmur: very close to the Dravidian murmuru, murmur
- chouraver (French slang)/steal: close to karav, steal in Dravidian, and cara, thief in Glazelian
- pâtir/suffer: close to the Dravidian patu, suffer
- paraître/appear: close to par, appear in Dravidian, and apara, appear in Glazelian
- pleuvoir/rain: close to poli, rain in Dravidian
- verser/pour: close to var, pour in Dravidian
- immerger/immerse: close to murgu, plunge in Dravidian
- taper/hit: close to tappu, hit in Dravidian
- terminer/finish: close to tirmanam, finish in Dravidian
- naître/be born: close to naru (pronounced natru), be born in Dravidian
- connaître/know: close to kan, know in Dravidian
- paver/pave: close to pavu, pave in Dravidian
- cumuler/accumulate: close to kummal, accumulate in Dravidian
- parler, parole/speak, word: close to paray, speak in Dravidian
- rouler, roue/drive, wheel: close to uruli, wheel (Drav), rota, wheel in Gaulish, close to urutu, drive (Drav)
- tarir, aride/run dry, dry: close to the Dravidian tarisu, dry land
- hululer, hulotte/hoot, tawny owl: close to uley, howl in Dravidian
- papa/dad: close to appa, dad in Dravidian
- maman/mum: close to Dravidian amman, mum, maman meaning grandmother in Dravidian, mama in Bur
- mec/guy: close to the Dravidian mac, husband, from ma, male in Dravidian
- fille, fils/daughter, son: could come from pillei, child in Dravidian, pilili, loved child in Burushaski
- mari, mariage/husband, marriage: could come from the Dravidian mari, son
- clan: close to kulan, family, clan in Dravidian
- charrue/plough: close to the Dravidian karu, plough, har in Burushaski
- pâture/pasture: close to the Dravidian pata, enclosure for domestic animals
- cime/peak: very close to the Dravidian cimmay, summit, cima in Glazelian
- campagne/countryside: very close to kampana in Dravidian, cultivated land
- orée/edge: close to oram, edge in Dravidian
- rivière/river: close to the Dravidian orivu, river, as ru, rivulet, is close to the Dravidian aru
- dune: close to the Dravidian dimmi, hill, don in Burushaski
- plaine/plain: close to pallam, plain in Dravidian
- caillou/stone: close to the Dravidian kal, caillou, which would have also given cairn in Celtic
- Sud/South: could come from the Dravidian sudu, heat
- gel/frost: could come from kulir, cold in Dravidian, ge, snow in Burushaski
- genou/knee: could come from the Dravidian kanu, knee
- cœur/heart: close to the Dravidian karal, heart and guru, heart in Burushaski
- cou, col/neck: close to kalam, neck in Dravidian
- pied/foot: close to padi, foot in Dravidian
- muqueuse, moucher/mucous, blow noise: could come from the Dravidian mukku, nose
- bouche/mouth: close to bukka, mouth in Dravidian, buk, throat in Burushaski
- molaire/molar: could come from mel, grind by masticating in Dravidian
- miel/honey: close to mel, sweet in Dravidian
- sucre/sugar: close to sakkaray, sugar in Dravidian, cane sugar, kannal in Dravidian
- pomme/apple: very close to pom, fruit in Dravidian, phamol, fruit in Burushaski and poma, fruit in Glazelian

- orange: from narangay, orange in Dravidian, nar, smell, from which could come nala, smell in Glozelian
- soupe, souper/soup, supper: close to suppu, eat a liquid food in Dravidian
- couteau/knife: close to katti, dagger, gladius, sword, knife in Dravidian
- bol/bowl: close to vallam, cup, round vessel in Dravidian
- bouteille/bottle: close to the Dravidian putil, bottle
- dîner/dinner: close to tin, eat in Dravidian
- saveur/savour: close to savi, taste, savour in Dravidian
- bataille/battle: very close to the Dravidian patay, battle
- cape, chape/cape, cope: very close to the Dravidian kappu, cover
- coton/cotton: very close to kottan, cotton in Dravidian
- cabane/hut: the French (and Celtic) word would also come from the Dravidian kappu, cover
- hutte/hut: close to kuti, hut, house in Dravidian, kutu, hut in Burushaski
- cave, caverne/cellar, cave: close to the Dravidian kavi, underground
- manoir/manor: close to the Dravidian mana, house
- château/castle: could stem from kottay, fort, which also influenced Gaulish
- salon, salle/living room, lessu, large room: close to salay, large room in Dravidian
- mur /wall: close to murru, wall in Dravidian
- tison/ember: could come from Dravidian ti, fire
- seau/bucket: could come from the Dravidian sal, bucket
- charbon/coal: close to the Dravidian kari, charcoal, coal
- mémoire/memory: could come from the Dravidian ninei, remember
- mot/word: identical to mot, word in Dravidian
- navire/boat: close to navay, boat in Dravidian, and to nau, boat in Glozelian and Gaulish
- ambre/amber: close to ambar, fossil resin in Dravidian
- plus, plusieurs/more, several: could come from the Dravidian pal, many
- période/period: could come from porudu, time in Dravidian, as pora in Slavic
- an, année/year: close to andu, year in Dravidian
- liesse/jubilation: close to lessu, religious jubilation in Drav, and litu, religious feast in Gaulish, as to liturgie
- sénile/senile: very close to the Dravidian senal, old
- calme/calm: very close to the Dravidian camm, calm
- valeureux/valiant: would come from the Dravidian val, strong, valiant
- mort/death: would come from margu, death in Dravidian, which could give morgue
- varié/varied: could come from the Dravidian veru, other, different
- aigu/sharp: close to akku, sharp in Dravidian
- sec/dry: close to sukku, dry in Dravidian
- petit/small: close to pittu, small in Dravidian
- vain: close to vin, vain in Dravidian
- hilare/laughing: close to killar, laughing in Dravidian
- beau, bel, belle/beautiful: close to pol, beautiful in Dravidian
- mûr/mature: close to mudir, mature in Dravidian
- furie/fury: close to veri, big anger in Dravidian
- vache/cow: close to baca, veal in Dravidian
- bouc/billy goat: close to bakar, ram in Dravidian, beskaret, ram in Burushaski
- bouc/billy goat: close to boka, billy goat in Dravidian, buc, billy goat in Burushaski
- chèvre/goat: close to kuri, goat in Dravidian
- bourrin (French slang)/horse: close to bur, horse in old Dravidian
- coq/cock: close to kokkokko, cock in Dravidian
- coucou/cuckoo: would come from Dravidian ku, scream
- papillon/butterfly: close to pupili, butterfly in Dravidian
- aigle/eagle: close to agil, eagle in Dravidian

I noticed as well correspondences between Slavic, Dravidian and Burushaski:

- voler/steal: karav in Dravidian, which can be linked to krast in Slavic
- peser/ weigh: vakay in Dravidian, linked to vaga, weight, scales in Slavic
- souffrir/suffer: mukku in Dravidian, linked to mučiti, torturer in Slavic
- frapper/beat: udey in Dravidian, close to udarit, beat in Slavic
- avoir besoin/need: nadu, close to nado in Russian, I need to
- aller, marcher/go, walk: sel in Dravidian, could be at the origin of the irregular past of go in c. sl., šel
- cuire/cook: varit, boil in Russian, could have derived from the Dravidian varu, cook
- jardin/garden: sad in Slavic, linked to sagu in Dravidian, plantation, saka, vegetable
- chat/cat: may, which can be linked to mačka, cat in Slavic
- maison/house: kuti, kuchtchu in Dravidian, kutu, hut in Bur, linked to kuća in Bosnian and to Finno-Ugrian
- nourriture/food: bukhta in Dravidian, bukhti, eat, would have given bukra, bread in Kartv, buchta in c. sl.
- froid/cold: kulir, cold in Dravidian, could have given kholod, cold in Russian
- pauvre/poor: bida in Dravidian, can be linked to bida, poverty in Slavic, biedny, poor in Slavic
- pauvre/poor: missukan in Dravidian, could have given siromasan, poor in Bosnian
- je/I: the Dravidian ya is identical to Slavic and close to French, as the Burushaski ya, ye
- orange: narangay in Drav gave naranča in Slavic, from nar, smell, from which came nar, grenade in c. sl.
- moitié/half: the Dravidian pal is very close to pol, half in Slavic

- court/short: kuru in Dravidian, is close to korotki in Russian, kratki in Slavic and court in French
- nuage/cloud: mugil in Dravidian, is close to mgla, fog in Polish
- hutte/hut: salaï in Dravidian, is close to šalaš in Russian
- sucre/sugar: sakkaray, close to sakhar in Russian
- chène/oak: dub, close to Drav tumb, kind of tree, Bur tom; Dravidians were at the origin of the cult of tree.
- gorge/throat: kural, gol, close to gorlo, throat in Russian, kerki, close to krk, throat in Czech
- forteresse/fortress: kula, could have given kula, tower in Bosnian
- sec/dry: sukku, close to sukhoy, suši in Slavic
- ce/this: avai, close to ovo in Bosnian
- sol/floor: dol in Dravidian, can be linked to na dole, down, in Slavic